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Master's Thesis

The Order Dimension of Grids and Products

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Zusammenfassung

Die Ordnungsdimension ist ein Maß der Komplexität partieller Ordnungen. Erstmals eingeführt von Dushnik und Miller [10] in 1941, hat die Ordnungsdimension einige Anwendungen in der Kombinatorik gefunden. Eine Frage die diesbezüglich von Anfang an offen stand, ist das Bestimmen der Dimension von Produkten partieller Ordnungen. Üblicherweise besteht zwischen Dimension und dem Produkt die Beziehung $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$. Für partielle Ordnungen stellt die rechte Seite dieser Gleichung aber nur eine obere Schranke dar. Das Verhältnis

$$\max(\dim(P), \dim(Q)) \leq \dim(P \times Q) \leq \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$$

ist für partielle Ordnungen P und Q bereits seit geraumer Zeit bekannt, jedoch wurden bis jetzt keine Beispiele gefunden für die $\dim(P \times Q) < \dim(P) + \dim(Q) - 2$ gilt. Es ist noch ein offenes Problem, ob solche Ordnungen existieren.

Wieder aufgegriffen haben wir diese Fragestellung aufgrund eines Problems, das Niklas Affolter formuliert hat. Er fragte sich, was die Ordnungsdimension der Ordnung ist, die daher rührt, dass man die Flächen eines Würfelgitters nach Inklusion ordnet. In diesem Zusammenhang lässt sich ein d -dimensionales Würfelgitter als d -Faches Produkt einer Zaun-Ordnung (siehe Abbildung 3.2) beschreiben. Mittels dieser Darstellung kann dann eine obere Schranke für die Dimension gezeigt werden. Das dafür verwendete Argument haben wir weiter ausgebaut um auch obere Schranken für Produkte mit Kronen (siehe C_n in Abbildung 1.1) zu bestimmen. Es stellt sich heraus, dass die Grundidee Reuter [21] bereits 1989 bekannt war. Dieser beschrieb eine Überdeckungseigenschaft die obere Schranken für Produkte liefert.

Die Arbeit ist folgendermaßen aufgebaut. In Kapitel 1 beschreiben wir die Hauptfragestellung und führen grundlegende Definitionen so wie bekannte Sätze und Vermutungen ein. Yannakakis [30] zeigte, dass das Bestimmen der Ordnungsdimension ein NP-schweres Problem ist. Um dies dennoch zu bewerkstelligen, werden in Kapitel 2 Methoden behandelt um die Dimension mithilfe von SAT- und MILP-Solvern zu berechnen. In Kapitel 3 wird die Dimension des Würfelgitters untersucht. Dabei zeigen wir auch eine neue Charakterisierung von Zaun-Ordnungen und geben obere Schranken für die Dimension von Produkten mit Zäunen und Kronen an. Kapitel 4 ist der bereits genannten Überdeckungseigenschaft gewidmet. Wir geben zuerst Reuters [21] ursprüngliche Definition wieder. Da diese auf Ferrers Relationen eingeführt wurde, geben wir eine kurze Einführung und verdeutlichen die Beziehung zwischen Ferrers Relationen und partiellen Ordnungen. Danach führen wir den Originalbeweis der Überdeckungseigenschaft aus und formulieren dann eine alternative Definition der Eigenschaft, welche eher mit unseren Ansätzen übereinstimmt. Zuletzt diskutieren wir in Kapitel 5 offenstehende Probleme und liefern einen kurzen Rückblick.

Introduction

It is hard to imagine modern mathematics without the concept of dimension. Nearly all branches of research – be it applied or theoretical – use the dimension of sets. Naturally, it has also found its way into the study of partially ordered sets. Formally introduced by Dushnik and Miller [10] in 1941, the order dimension of a poset has been an important invariant of partially ordered sets ever since.

In almost every context that dimension appears in, its relation to the cartesian product is set in stone. One expects that equations of the form $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$ and $\dim(P \cup Q) = \max(\dim(P), \dim(Q))$ hold. This is not quite the case for order dimension. While the equality for the union mostly holds true, in many cases the product deviates from the usual equality. Often $\dim(P) + \dim(Q)$ just represents an upper bound. This upper bound and conditions for the aforementioned deviation have been studied by a few noteworthy authors. The primary published results are due to Trotter [27], Reuter [21, 22] and Lin [20], the latest of which has been published in 1991.

This thesis will revisit many of their results. In Chapter 1 we give an introduction into the topic. We establish important notation, definitions, the objects of study and the most important results from relevant literature.

During our research it was imperative that we could quickly generate examples and calculate their dimension. For this purpose, we have spent some effort to investigate methods of determining the dimension of partial orders. Using modern tools such as SAT and MILP-Solvers yields promising results, far exceeding openly available tools. We present these results in Chapter 2.

In Chapter 3 we discuss the problems we originally set out to study when we started working on this thesis. We determine the dimension of the face lattice of a d -dimensional grid by proving upper and lower bounds for the dimension of products with fence posets. This result is then used to establish a new characterization of fences. Subsequently, we use the ideas we employed during the proofs to determine upper bounds for crown posets as well.

Then in Chapter 4 we will see that the approach we utilized to derive upper bounds for fences and crowns has already been used and generalized by Reuter to work on larger classes of posets. These results were mostly formulated with Ferrers dimension in mind, which is a useful but rarely discussed generalization of order dimension. We describe a reinterpretation that is more in line with the common view on order dimension and complete some of the proofs that Reuter only hinted at.

1. Introductory Concepts

Order dimension was initially introduced by Dushnik and Miller in 1941. Since its discovery it has played an important role in many different fields of combinatorics. A large question, that has remained open since its inception, is its relation to the cartesian product. Usually, one would expect that $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$ holds for any property called “dimension”. In practice, this seems to be close to the truth for posets, but there often seems to be a slight defect in this equation where the left hand side ends up being too small. As of today, there are no non-trivial lower bounds for this defect, yet there is no known example where this defect is larger than 2.

In this chapter we aim to give a brief introduction to order dimension and introduce the cartesian product of partially ordered sets. We will discuss many of the core results from literature, which we will be repeatedly making use of throughout this thesis.

1.1. Order Dimension

Most of the results and definitions in this section can be reviewed in more detail in [26].

A *partially ordered set* or *poset* $P = (X, \leq_P)$ consists of a finite set $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and a reflexive, transitive and antisymmetric relation \leq_P on X . We call $x, y \in X$ *comparable* if $x \leq_P y$ or $y \leq_P x$ and *incomparable* otherwise. We will often write $x \parallel y$ if x and y are incomparable and write $x < y$ if $x \leq y$ and $x \neq y$. If P has a unique minimum, we will denote it by $\mathbf{0}$ and analogously a unique maximum is denoted by $\mathbf{1}$. The set of incomparable pairs of an order is defined as $\text{inc}(P) := \{(x, y) \in X \times X \mid x \parallel y\}$. Be aware that these are ordered pairs, so $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$ if and only if $(y, x) \in \text{inc}(P)$.

A *linear extension* of a poset $P = (X, \leq_P)$ is a total order $L = (X, \leq_L)$ on the same set of elements X that contains P . In other words, if $x, y \in X$ with $x \leq_P y$, then $x \leq_L y$ and for all $x, y \in X$ it holds that $x \leq_L y$ or $y \leq_L x$. Szpilrajn [25] originally proved that for each $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$, there is a linear extension L of P , such that $x <_L y$ in L and thus $y \not\leq_L x$. This implies that a poset P is the intersection of all its linear extensions.

Defining dimension now comes naturally. The *Dushnik-Miller dimension* or *order dimension* of P is the smallest $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that P is the intersection of t linear extensions. We will usually just refer to this as the *dimension* of a poset, denoted by $\dim(P)$. A set of linear extensions of P , such that their intersection is equal to P , is called a *realizer* of P . As such, the dimension equals the cardinality of a minimum size realizer. We will say that a linear extension L of P *inverts* or *reverses* $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$ if $y <_L x$ and define the set of pairs inverted by L as $\text{inv}(L) := \{(a, b) \mid b <_L a\}$. Bear in mind that for $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$, $x \not\leq_L y$ if and only if $y <_L x$, so a realizer R is exactly a set of

linear extensions such that $\text{inc}(P) \subseteq \bigcup_{L \in R} \text{inv}(L)$. In other words, each $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$ is inverted by some $L \in R$.

Figure 1.1.: Partial orders and their dimension.

Figure 1.1 shows a few examples of posets and their dimension. Let us briefly discuss some classic examples. The k -chain L_k has dimension 1, as it already constitutes a total order. Any antichain A_k , with $k \geq 2$ has $\dim(A_k) = 2$. This is because any total order on the same set of elements is a linear extension, hence we can take the elements from left-to-right and right-to-left to get two extensions that form a realizer. For examples with arbitrarily large dimension consider the Standard Example S_n with $\dim(S_n) = n$. It is formally defined as $S_n = (X_n, \leq_n)$ where $X_n = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \cup \{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$ and $a_i \leq_n b_j \iff i \neq j$. To see that $\dim(S_n) \leq n$, recognize that for $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, if the pair (a_k, b_k) is inverted by some L , then all pairs $(a_k, a_l), (b_l, b_k)$ for $k \neq l$ are also inverted, since $a_l <_L b_k <_L a_k <_L b_l$ in L . $\dim(S_n) \geq n$ holds because only one of the n -pairs (a_t, b_t) may be inverted at a time.

There are a few important facts when it comes to dimension, that the reader must be aware of in order to follow many of the arguments throughout this thesis. First, observe that dimension obeys a natural “monotonicity”. For posets $P = (X, \leq_P)$ and $Q = (Y, \leq_Q)$, Q is an *induced subposet* or just *subposet* of P if $Y \subseteq X$ and $x \leq_Q y$ if and only if $x \leq_P y$. Now any linear extension of P also yields a linear extension of Q and thus the following fact is apparent.

Fact 1.1. If Q is an induced subposet of P , then $\dim(Q) \leq \dim(P)$.

In turn, we call a poset k -*irreducible* if $\dim(P) = k$, but $\dim(Q) < k$ for all strict subposets Q of P .

A question that immediately arises when studying order dimension is the following. For a set $S \subseteq \text{inc}(P)$, when can we find a linear extension that covers all pairs of S ? Consider

a finite sequence of incomparable pairs $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ such that $x_i \leq_P y_{i+1}$, where indices are viewed cyclically. If L inverts all (x_i, y_i) then

$$y_1 <_L x_1 \leq_L y_2 <_L x_2 \leq_L \dots \leq_L y_n <_L x_n.$$

But by assumption we also have $x_n \leq_P y_1$, which is a contradiction. Thus we define an *alternating cycle* as exactly such a sequence of pairs. As it turns out, this criterion is all we need.

Fact 1.2 ([26]). Let $S \subseteq \text{inc}(P)$, then there is a linear extension L of P that inverts all pairs of S if and only if S contains no alternating cycle.

Proof. The previous argument already shows that one cannot invert all pairs of an alternating cycle. We still need to show that there is such a linear extension if S contains no alternating cycles. We use the classic way of constructing a linear extension by repeatedly picking and then removing minimal elements of P , additionally making sure that for $(a, b) \in S$ we avoid selecting a , unless b has already been taken. If all elements are eventually selected, we constructed an extension that inverts all pairs in S . Suppose the procedure does not complete, that is we reach a point where for each remaining minimal element $x \in M$ there exists some y_x , such that $(x, y_x) \in S$, but y_x has not been selected yet. For each such y_x there is $\bar{x} \in M$, with $\bar{x} \leq y_x$, because M consists of all minimal Elements. If we now view $V := \{(x, y_x) \mid x \in M\}$ as a directed graph with arcs $\{((x, y_x), (\hat{x}, \hat{y}_x)) \mid x \leq \hat{y}_x\}$, then, by the previous argument, each element in V has an ingoing edge. But this is only possible if the graph contains a cycle and cycles in V are alternating cycles. \square

Next, recall the Standard Example we mentioned above. We claimed that if (a_t, b_t) is reversed, then all pairs (a_t, a_k) with $k \neq t$ are also reversed, because $a_k < b_t < a_t$ must then hold. This idea is encapsulated within a well-known concept. Consider incomparable pairs $(x, y), (v, w) \in \text{inc}(P)$. If $w \leq_P y$ and $x \leq_P v$, then inverting (x, y) in a linear extension L implies

$$w \leq_L y <_L x \leq_L v.$$

This means that inverting the pair (x, y) forces one to also invert pair (v, w) , so it is enough to just worry about inverting (x, y) . This motivates the following definition. We call $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$ a *critical pair* if $z <_P x$ implies $z <_P y$ and $y <_P z$ implies $x <_P z$. We denote the set of critical pairs of P by $\text{crit}(P)$.

Fact 1.3. A set of linear extensions inverts all incomparable pairs if and only if it inverts all critical pairs.

Of course this combines nicely with Fact 1.2. That is, there is a linear extension inverting all critical pairs in $S \subseteq \text{crit}(P)$ if and only if S contains no alternating cycle.

1.2. Cartesian Products

The *cartesian product* or just *product* of two posets is defined as follows. For posets $P = (X_P, \leq_P)$ and $Q = (X_Q, \leq_Q)$ the poset $P \times Q$ is given by $P \times Q := (X_P \times X_Q, \leq_{P \times Q})$ where $(p_1, q_1) \leq_{P \times Q} (p_2, q_2)$ if $p_1 \leq p_2$ and $q_1 \leq q_2$. In particular, this means that $(p_1, q_1) \parallel (p_2, q_2)$ in exactly one of the four cases: $p_1 \parallel p_2, q_1 \parallel q_2, p_1 <_P p_2$ and $q_1 >_Q q_2$, or $p_1 >_P p_2$ and $q_1 <_Q q_2$.

Figure 1.2.: Cartesian Product of Posets

The most well-known poset that occurs as the product of posets is the Boolean Lattice B_n . It is defined as $B_n = (X_n, \subseteq)$ where X_n is the power set of $\{1, \dots, n\}$. It is easy to see that this is isomorphic to the n -times product of a one chain with itself. For its dimension, we get $\dim(B_n) = n$, because all of the critical pairs are between the 1-element and n -element subsets, and the induced subposet of these elements is isomorphic to the Standard Example S_n .

It is unclear when the dimension of products was first studied. It arises quite naturally from the definition, but has not been mentioned in the original paper by Dushnik and Miller. The earliest work we could verify was by Kelly and Trotter [18] in 1982, but they mention earlier unpublished notes by Baker and others. Accordingly, the following result is due to mathematical folklore, but lays the groundwork for all that is to come.

Fact 1.4. Let P and Q be arbitrary posets. Then

$$\max(\dim(P), \dim(Q)) \leq \dim(P \times Q) \leq \dim(P) + \dim(Q).$$

Proof. For any $p \in P$, we get that $\{p\} \times Q \cong Q$. As $\{p\} \times Q$ is a subposet of $P \times Q$, this implies that $\dim(Q) \leq \dim(P \times Q)$. Applying analogous reasoning to P yields $\dim(P) \leq \dim(P \times Q)$.

To prove the upper bound, let P_1, \dots, P_n be a realizer of P and Q_1, \dots, Q_m be a realizer of Q . We will define an appropriate realizer of $P \times Q$. Let L_1, \dots, L_{n+m} be a set of linear extensions of $P \times Q$. For $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, we set $(p, q) \leq_{L_i} (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q})$ if either $p <_{P_i} \tilde{p}$ or $p = \tilde{p}$ and $q \leq_{Q_1} \tilde{q}$. For $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we set $(p, q) \leq_{L_{n+j}} (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q})$ if $q <_{Q_j} \tilde{q}$ or $q = \tilde{q}$ and $p \leq_{P_1} \tilde{p}$. Essentially, for L_1, \dots, L_n we sort the entries by P_i in the P component and for L_{n+1}, \dots, L_m we sort the entries by Q_j in the Q component. To see that this forms a realizer, let $((p, q), (\tilde{p}, \tilde{q})) \in \text{inc}(P \times Q)$. Now there are four cases to consider. If $p \parallel \tilde{p}$ then there is P_i such that $\tilde{p} <_{P_i} p$, as the P_i form a realizer of P . Therefore $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) <_{L_i} (p, q)$. The case for $q \parallel \tilde{q}$ is similar. If $p >_P \tilde{p}$ and $q <_Q \tilde{q}$, then in each L_i for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ we have that $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) <_{L_i} (p, q)$. Again, the case for $p <_P \tilde{p}$ and $q <_Q \tilde{q}$ is similar. \square

There are many known examples for which this upper bound is achieved, but it is not hard to see that this is not always the case. Trivially, if A_n is an antichain, then $A_n \times P$ is just the n -times disjoint union of P , which has dimension equal to $\max(\dim(P), 2)$ and thus $\dim(A_n \times P) = \dim(P) + \dim(A_n) - 2$ if $\dim(P) \geq 2$. Quite surprisingly, there are no known examples where $\dim(P \times Q) < \dim(P) + \dim(Q) - 2$, yet the trivial bound we proved in Fact 1.4 is still the best known lower bound. Of course, for very large $\dim(P)$ and $\dim(Q)$ this gap is immense. The most important unsolved conjectures in regards to this are as follows.

Conjecture 1.5 ([27]). *For every m, n with $1 \leq m \leq n$, there exist posets P and Q with $\dim(P) = m$, $\dim(Q) = n$ and $\dim(P \times Q) = n$.*

Conjecture 1.6 ([18]). *For arbitrary posets P and Q , $\dim(P \times Q) \geq \dim(P) + \dim(Q) - 2$.*

Of course, these two conjectures directly contradict each other. Conjecture 1.5 was proposed by Trotter, when he proved that for the Standard Example S_n with $n \geq 3$, it holds that $\dim(S_n) = n$ but $\dim(S_n \times S_n) = 2n - 2$ [27].

The earliest mention of Conjecture 1.6 was by Kelly and Trotter in 1982. Conceptually, one just needs to find a counterexample to disprove this conjecture but these have not been found yet, if they exist. It could very well be that counterexamples only exist in high dimension, but determining order dimension is often quite challenging, which makes constructing intricate high dimensional orders with precise bounds on the dimension difficult. The most noteworthy result on this is one by Reuter, where he disproved an earlier conjecture of Trotter.

Theorem 1.7 ([21]). *$\dim(P \times P) \geq 4$ for all P with $\dim(P) \geq 3$.*

We will give the proof of this statement in Section 3.2. Reuter was unable to prove whether $\dim(P \times Q) \geq 4$ for P and Q with $\dim(P) = \dim(Q) = 3$. We also did not complete this proof, but we provide strong evidence that this is true in Section 2.4, which, in turn, would disprove Conjecture 1.5.

Many cases for which the upper bound $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$ is achieved, have already been known since 1961. The proof is usually attributed to an unpublished note by Baker.

Theorem 1.8 ([1]). *Let P and Q be posets, both of which have $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$. Then $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$.*

Proof. Let $R = \{L_1, \dots, L_k\}$ be a realizer of $P \times Q$. Denote the respective ones and zeroes of P and Q by $\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_P$ and $\mathbf{0}_Q, \mathbf{1}_Q$. By definition of $P \times Q$ the elements $(\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q)$ and $(\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q)$ are incomparable. So let $R_1 = \{L_i \in R \mid (\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q) <_{L_i} (\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q)\}$ and $R_2 = \{L_i \in R \mid (\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q) <_{L_i} (\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q)\}$. Now let $x_1, x_2 \in P$ with $x_1 \parallel x_2$, then we claim

that the incomparable pair $(x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q), (x_2, \mathbf{0}_Q)$ must be inverted in R_1 . This is because for all $L \in R_2$ we get

$$(x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q) \leq_L (\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q) <_L (\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q) \leq_L (x_2, \mathbf{1}_Q).$$

So the incomparable pair $((x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q), (x_2, \mathbf{1}_Q))$ is not inverted in R_2 . Hence it must be inverted in R_1 which then implies

$$(x_2, \mathbf{0}_Q) <_L (x_2, \mathbf{1}_Q) <_L (x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q)$$

for some $L \in R_1$. This means that the pair $(x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q), (x_2, \mathbf{0}_Q)$ is also inverted in L_1 . Therefore R_1 must invert all incomparable $(x_1, \mathbf{0}_Q), (x_2, \mathbf{0}_Q)$. In other words, R_1 restricted to elements of $P \times \{\mathbf{0}_Q\}$ forms a realizer of $P \times \{\mathbf{0}_Q\}$ and since $P \cong P \times \{\mathbf{0}_Q\}$, it must hold that $|R_1| \geq \dim(P)$.

With an analogous argument it can be shown that $|R_2| \geq \dim(Q)$ and thus $\dim(P \times Q) \geq \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$. \square

This shows that, while the dimension is not influenced by whether a poset has $\mathbf{0}$ or $\mathbf{1}$, it is often crucial to determining the dimension of the product. That minimal and maximal elements are important in this way can also be seen by characterizing the critical pairs of $P \times Q$. We discovered this characterization independently, although this has also been described by Lin in 1991. We will denote the set of minimal or maximal elements of a poset by $\min(P)$ or $\max(P)$ respectively. We will also say for elements x, y of $P = (X, \leq)$ that y covers x if $x < y$ and there is no other element z with $x < z < y$. The cover graph is then given by $G = (X, E)$ with $E = \{\{x, y\} \mid y \text{ covers } x\}$.

Theorem 1.9 ([20]). *Let P, Q be posets where x_1, x_2 are elements of P and y_1, y_2 are elements of Q . Then $((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2))$ is a critical pair of $P \times Q$ if and only if one of the following conditions holds.*

1. (x_1, x_2) is a critical pair of P , y_1 is a minimal element of Q and y_2 is a maximal element of Q , such that $y_1 \leq y_2$.
2. (x_1, x_2) is an incomparable pair of P , x_1 is a minimal element of P , x_2 is a maximal element of P , y_1 is a minimal element of Q and y_2 is a maximal element of Q .
3. $x_1 < x_2$, $x_1 \in \min(P)$, $x_2 \in \max(P)$ and y_1 covers y_2 , such that y_1 is the only element covering y_2 and y_2 is the only element covered by y_1 .
4. (y_1, y_2) is a critical pair of P , x_1 is a minimal element of Q and x_2 is a maximal element of Q , such that $x_1 \leq x_2$.
5. (y_1, y_2) is an incomparable pair of P , y_1 is a minimal element of P , y_2 is a maximal element of P , x_1 is a minimal element of Q and x_2 is a maximal element of Q .
6. $y_1 < y_2$, $y_1 \in \min(P)$, $y_2 \in \max(P)$ and x_1 covers x_2 , such that x_1 is the only element covering x_2 and x_2 is the only element covered by x_1 .

We will omit the proof here, as it mostly just involves a simple case distinction over the incomparable pairs of $P \times Q$. Unfortunately, this is a somewhat cumbersome and technical characterization, so we will usually just make use of this implicitly when describing the critical pairs of some products.

2. Calculating Dimension

After deciding that one of our main goals in this thesis would be to determine the dimension of products of orders, it became immediately apparent that we needed a good way to calculate the dimension in order to test hypotheses and verify examples. Yannakakis [30] showed that determining the order dimension of a partial order is NP-Hard using a reduction from the graph coloring problem, hence finding an efficient algorithm is difficult. Furthermore, there are few publicly available tools to calculate poset dimension. The SageMath software system [24] does provide an implementation, but this is often far too slow, even for comparatively small examples.

There have also been few published attempts at finding empirically fast algorithms. Koppen [19] as well as Yáñez and Montero [29] have described potential algorithms, but they neither seemed easy to implement, nor was it likely that they would greatly outperform our methods. We have primarily considered two different approaches to this problem. Both of them involve reductions to NP-Complete problems and then using modern solving tools to calculate a solution.

2.1. Selecting Pairs with SAT

There is a sensible way to view the decision problem, whether an order admits a realizer of size at most n , as an instance of SAT. This is best derived from the technical definition of a poset. A total order is a reflexive, antisymmetric and transitive relation requiring that for each pair exactly one of its orientations is chosen. To transfer this over to a SAT instance, we can ignore the pairs obtained from reflexivity, as they are always contained. Antisymmetry and the need to choose exactly one orientation for each pair can be encoded by the variables themselves, as we have to make exactly one of two choices for each variable in any assignment. Transitivity is then encoded by the clauses of the SAT formula. Since transitivity constraints consist of simple implications on at most three literals, this is an encoding that SAT is well-suited to.

The concrete formulation we came up with is as follows. Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a poset. Define a variable x_{ab} for each unordered incomparable pair $\{a, b\} \subseteq X, a \parallel b$, where the order of (a, b) is fixed arbitrarily. Let V be the set of these variables. For each ordered pair (a, b) with $a \neq b$ declare a corresponding literal

$$l(a, b) := \begin{cases} x_{ab} & \text{if } x_{ab} \in V \\ \neg x_{ba} & \text{if } x_{ba} \in V \end{cases}.$$

This describes the aforementioned choice for each pair. In order to make sure that these choices obey transitivity constraints, add clauses

$$C_{abc} := \neg l(a, b) \vee \neg l(b, c) \vee l(a, c) \text{ for all } \{a, b, c\} \subseteq X.$$

Solving just this SAT formula would return some permutation of the elements of X . To find a linear extension of P now just fix the literals $l(a, b)$ as 1 for all (a, b) with $a \leq b$. Fixing one such literal can be accomplished by adding an additional clause with just $l(a, b)$. Alternatively we can also perform some preprocessing manually. Essentially, one ignores a clause C if $l(a, b) \in C$ and remove $\neg l(a, b)$ from C if $\neg l(a, b) \in C$. Let \widehat{C}_{abc} be the clause after applying this reduction. Then we set

$$L := \bigwedge_{a, b, c \in X} \widehat{C}_{abc}.$$

Now any satisfying assignment of L will correspond to a linear extension of P . Finding a realizer of size k now requires little additional work. Let L_i be an independent copy of L for $1 \leq i \leq k$ and denote its literals by $l(a, b, i)$. Introducing clauses

$$C_{ab} = l(a, b, 1) \vee \dots \vee l(a, b, k)$$

for each $(a, b) \in \text{inc}(P)$ will ensure that each incomparable pair is covered by the realizer at least once. Thus, the final formula is given by

$$S_k := \bigwedge_{i=1}^k L_i \wedge \bigwedge_{(a, b) \in \text{inc}(P)} C_{ab}. \quad (2.1)$$

If the formula is satisfiable, recovering the realizer from a satisfying assignment is not hard. For fixed i , the comparable pairs of P form a total order with those a, b where $l(a, b, i)$ was set to 1. Calculating a topological order of the directed comparability graph of P with the added (a, b) will then give the desired result. Finally, determining the order dimension now just involves finding the minimal k such that S_k is satisfiable.

When implementing this approach, it is sensible to apply the SAT formula to a subposet of P with the same dimension. The natural choice for this is the poset induced by $\{x \mid (x, y) \in \text{crit}(P)\} \cup \{y \mid (x, y) \in \text{crit}(P)\}$. This must have the same dimension as P according to Fact 1.3. We did implement this, but did generally not see significant performance gains. It seems probable that the SAT solver can learn which pairs are being forced by other pairs from the given clauses and thus determine that mostly only the critical pairs are important.

2.2. Digraph Coloring

In SageMath, order dimension is calculated by determining a coloring of the hypergraph of incomparable pairs. As described by Felsner and Trotter [11], it is defined by $G = (\text{inc}(P), E)$, with E defined as the set of $S \subseteq \text{inc}(P)$ that contain an alternating cycle but where all subsets of S do not contain an alternating cycle. In general, this hypergraph

may contain a very large number of edges, so generating this entire hypergraph ahead of time is not viable in practice. This can be remedied by using a cutting planes like approach, where one starts with a subset of the hypergraph's and attempts to find a solution such that no edge of this subset is monochromatic. After that one checks if the found solution contains an alternating cycle. This can be done efficiently using depth first search. If it does contain a cycle, add the cycle to the constraints and reoptimize. Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) solvers offer convenient interfaces for such an implementation. In particular, the reoptimization can be done efficiently without having to start over all the way from the beginning.

This approach can be modified by working with the hypergraph of critical pairs instead, which is defined in the same way but on the vertex set $\text{crit}(P)$. We wanted to find a polynomial space encoding for this hypergraph coloring. As it turns out we can reformulate this as a generalization of the common graph coloring problem. Define the directed graph $G = (\text{crit}(P), A)$ where $A := \{((x, y), (\hat{x}, \hat{y})) \mid x \leq \hat{y}\}$. Then cycles in G exactly correspond to alternating cycles in P . Thus we can recontextualize the problem as follows.

Given a directed graph $G = (V, A)$, find a coloring such that the induced subgraph of each color class does not contain a directed cycle. We call such a coloring with k -colors a *circular k -coloring*. For a graph, the smallest k such that a circular k -coloring exists is called the *circular coloring number*. The corresponding decision problems are in NP, as any solution is verifiable in polynomial time via depth first search. More so, if each edge exists in both directions, then a circular coloring corresponds to a common coloring of the underlying undirected graph. As such it is also NP-hard, because it constitutes a generalization of the usual graph coloring problem. Hence we can find a SAT or Mixed Integer Linear Programming formulation to calculate the circular coloring number. We will not delve much deeper into such colorings, but Bokal et al. [5] give a comprehensive introduction for the curious reader.

2.2.1. Mixed Integer Linear Program

We will present a Mixed Integer Linear Program to determine whether a graph admits a circular k -coloring. Let $G = (V, A)$ be a directed graph and $n = |V|$. Then the following linear program is feasible if and only if G admits a circular k -coloring.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize} && 0 \\ & \text{subject to} && x_{v,i} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } v \in V, 1 \leq i \leq k \\ & && \sum_{i=1}^k x_{v,i} = 1 \quad \text{for all } v \in V \\ & && \bar{x}_{w,i} - \bar{x}_{v,i} - nx_{w,i} \geq 1 - n \quad \text{for all } (v, w) \in E, 1 \leq i \leq k \end{aligned}$$

Here, the variables $x_{v,i}$ represent whether vertex v belongs to color class i . The equations $\sum_{i=1}^k x_{v,i} = 1$ therefore enforce that each vertex belongs to exactly one color class. The variables $\bar{x}_{v,i}$ are being introduced to make sure that each color class does not contain a cycle. The basic idea is to find a topological ordering of the induced subgraph of $V_i := \{v \in V \mid x_{v,i} = 1\}$, which only exists if the subgraph is acyclic. To accomplish this, we started out with equations $\bar{x}_{w,i} - \bar{x}_{v,i} \geq 1$ for each edge (v, w) , so each vertex gets

assigned a larger value than its predecessor. But remember that vertices may not be contained in V_i , so we add $n(1 - \bar{x}_{w,i})$ to the left hand side of the constraint to disable it when $w \notin V_i$.

We can also modify the above linear program to compute the size of a minimum directed k -coloring directly by solving

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{minimize} && \sum_{i=1}^k c_i \\
& \text{subject to} && c_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq i \leq k \\
& && x_{v,i} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } v \in V, 1 \leq i \leq k \\
& && x_{v,i} \leq c_i \quad \text{for all } v \in V, 1 \leq i \leq k \\
& && \sum_{i=1}^k x_{v,i} = 1 \quad \text{for all } v \in V \\
& && \bar{x}_{w,i} - \bar{x}_{v,i} - nx_{w,i} \geq 1 - n \quad \text{for all } (v, w) \in E, 1 \leq i \leq k.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

In this case we set k to some appropriate upper bound for the circular coloring number of G . The variable c_i is now set to 1 if the color class i is used. Minimizing $\sum_{i=1}^k c_i$ then yields the circular coloring number.

2.2.2. SAT Formula

Although a SAT-based formulation is less convenient to implement for this approach, we were still curious to see how it performed in comparison. The main idea is to encode the criterion that the induced subgraph of each color class is cycle-free by encoding a type of graph search within the SAT formula. If we have a variable for each vertex, and each variable is implied by its predecessor, then setting a start vertex s to 1 will result in all reachable vertices also being set to 1. Now, if we instead set all vertices in the neighborhood $w \in \delta^+(s)$ to 1 without specifying s , and the implications force s to be set to 1, then there is a path from s to s , and the graph contains a cycle.

With these considerations, we can arrive at the following SAT formula. To decide whether a graph $G = (V, A)$ admits a circular k -coloring, introduce a new variable $x_{v,j}$ for each vertex $v \in V$ and color $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. These will correspond to the chosen vertices for each color class. Then also introduce a new variable $x_{v,j}^w$ for each $v, w \in V$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. These variables will represent the graph on which we will run our graph search to determine whether the induced subgraph contains a cycle.

For clauses, set

$$C_v := x_{v,1} \vee \dots \vee x_{v,k}.$$

For each edge $a = (w_s, w_t) \in A$, $v \in V$, $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, declare clauses

$$C_{a,j}^v := \neg x_{w_s,j} \vee \neg x_{w_s,j}^v \vee x_{w_t,j}^v.$$

For all v and $w \in \delta^+(v)$, add

$$C_{w,j}^v := \neg x_{v,j} \vee x_{w,j}^v.$$

Finally, set

$$C_{v,j} := \neg x_{v,j} \vee \neg x_{v,j}^v.$$

The desired SAT formula in Conjunctive Normal Form then is the conjunction of all these defined clauses. We omit a formal proof of correctness here, and just discuss the underlying ideas. In a satisfying assignment, the vertex v is contained in color class j if $x_{v,j}$ is set to 1. Be aware that a vertex may be contained in multiple color classes, but this can be remedied by removing the vertex from all but one color class.

Now, suppose the j -th color class of a satisfying assignment contains a cycle. Then there are vertices v_1, \dots, v_k such that $x_{v_i,j}$ is set to 1 and $(v_i, v_{i+1}) \in A$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. The clause $C_{v_2,j}^{v_1}$ and $x_{v_1,j} = 1$ consequently imply that $x_{v_2,j}^{v_1} = 1$. This in turn, in combination with $x_{v_2,j} = 1$ and $C_{(v_2,v_3),j}^{v_1}$ will then imply that $x_{v_3,j}$ is equal to one. Continuing this reasoning along the edges of the cycle will result in $x_{v_1,j}^{v_1} = 1$. But this, and our initial assumption of $x_{v_1,j} = 1$ contradicts clause $C_{v_1,j}$. Thus, no color class of a satisfying assignment contains a cycle. The converse, that each directed k -coloring results in a satisfying assignment, can be proven by defining an assignment on the variables, where $x_{v_i,j} = 1$ if v_i is in color class j as well as $x_{w,j}^v = 1$ if $x_{v,j} = 1$ and w is reachable from v in the induced subgraph of color class j .

While this idea is interesting, it did not end up being very performant, likely due to the large amount of additional variables required. Having to run depth-first search for each vertex solely through a SAT equation obviously carries significant additional cost. That said, directly modifying the solver to run a performant graph search and then adding the cycles could run well.

2.3. Breaking Symmetries

A disadvantage of all of the above formulations is that there are at least $k!$ symmetries when checking whether an order has dimension k , as we can permute the linear extensions in any formula to get equivalent assignments. Consequently, for large k , this likely heavily impacts performance when the formula is unsatisfiable, as there are many more paths for the solver to explore. There are two clear ways to fix this. First, add additional constraints to the formula such that these symmetries are eliminated. Second, modify the solver directly so these paths are not explored in the first place. With our formulation, removing the symmetries by modifying the clauses required a large amount of additional variables and clauses, to the point where the improvements from removing the symmetries often ended up outweighing the benefits. But this is likely to change as k increases and we never rarely worked with k larger than 6. When successfully implemented, modifying the solver would not have that same issue. The difficulty here lies in the technical real-world issues of heavily modifying an unknown codebase in a programming language we are not entirely familiar with.

To break the symmetries, we opted to add the condition that the found assignments must be in lexicographic order. Suppose we have two sequences of variables $x = x_1, \dots, x_n$ and $y = y_1, \dots, y_n$. The constraint that x is lexicographically larger than y can be described as follows. Let $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. If $x_i = y_i$ for all $i < k$, then the assignment $x_k = 0, y_k = 1$ is forbidden. We encode these constraints by introducing additional variables c_i for $i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$. We want c_i to be an indicator of whether $x_i = y_i$, so

we add clauses $(x_i \vee y_i \vee \neg c_i)$ and $(\neg x_i \vee \neg y_i \vee \neg c_i)$. Now we can complete this by adding $(\neg c_1 \vee \dots \vee \neg c_{k-1} \vee x_i \vee \neg y_i)$ to achieve the desired constraints.

2.4. Performance and Results

To get an idea of the performance of these methods we have compared a few test cases in Table 2.1. The tested algorithms are as follows. INC is the SAT formula without reductions or symmetry breaking from Section 2.1. INC-ASYM is the same formula with symmetry breaking added. Analogously RED is the same formula, but reduced to a smaller poset and RED-ASYM includes symmetry breaking. DIRG-MILP and DIRG-SAT describe the MILP or SAT approach from Section 2.2 respectively. The algorithm used by SageMath is not represented in the table, as it is too slow to produce a result for any of the examples in a reasonable time frame.

We compare a few selected test cases in Table 2.1. $Z_5 \times Z_5$ is the product of Z_5 with itself, R is a randomly generated 5-dimensional poset, D is the face lattice of the dodecahedron, B_7 is the 7-dimensional Boolean Lattice and S_9 is the 9-dimensional Standard Example.

We have used state-of-the-art solvers Kissat [4, 3] to solve SAT formulas and Gurobi [14] to solve MILPs. To keep the comparison fair, all of these algorithms, but not the solvers, have been implemented in Python. Note that none of these programs have been rigorously optimized, so this comparison is only meant to give a rough indication of performance.

Poset	Time(s)					
	INC	INC-ASYM	RED	RED-ASYM	DIRG-MILP	DIRG-SAT
$Z_5 \times Z_5$	0.639	0.866	0.700	0.889	27.968	36.252
R	1.267	2.400	1.307	2.353	30.346	59.158
D	2.145	4.813	1.187	1.383	23.163	36.46
B_7	44.490	156.875	1.886	1.910	1.050	1.769
S_9	1.410	1.106	1.393	1.110	0.258	1.492

Table 2.1.: Performance of methods for calculating order dimension.

The results seem to make it pretty clear that the methods INC, INC-ASYM, RED, RED-ASYM from Section 2.1 work quite well in practice. Reducing the size of the poset to a smaller poset can have significant results, if the number of incomparable pairs is much larger than the number of critical pairs.

The methods from Section 2.2 have not performed very well in practice. For examples where the number of critical pairs is much lower than the number of incomparable pairs, such as the Standard Example or the Boolean Lattice, they do outperform the other methods but this was not worth it in general. That said, because algorithms for finding a circular coloring of a digraph have not been explored much, it seems possible that there are still significant performance gains to be made.

We have made the Python implementations for all of these methods publicly available [28] and are in the process of contributing an implementation of INC to SageMath.

We have also written a significantly faster implementation of INC in the Rust programming language. This made it possible to, for example, calculate the order dimension of the 24-cell regular 4-dimensional polytope in less than one minute.

We have also mostly verified Theorem 1.7 by calculating products of 3-irreducible posets with each other. These results can be viewed in detail in Appendix A. Because some of the families of 3-irreducible posets are infinite, this does not constitute a complete proof, but it is plausible that each element of such infinite families behaves similarly with regards to the product. Indeed, observing the table of results one is lead to believe that the following conjecture also holds.

Conjecture 2.1. *Let P, Q be posets with $3 \leq \dim(P)$ and $3 \leq \dim(Q)$. Then $\dim(P \times Q) \geq 4$.*

The table also reveals that the results are highly regular. Products with A always have dimension 4. All other products have dimension 5 unless both of the posets are among F, G and J , in which case the dimension is equal to 6. This means that, at least for 3-irreducible posets, we can describe the dimension of products as follows. Set $d(A) = 2$, $d(F) = d(G) = d(J) = 0$ and $d(P) = 1$ for all other 3-irreducible P . Then for 3-irreducible posets P, Q we get $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q) - \max(d(P), d(Q))$. In Chapter 4 we will give a description of what this factor d represents.

3. Grids, Fences and Crowns

A common appearance of partial orders in the wider mathematical landscape are the face lattices of polyhedra. For some polyhedron A , its face lattice is defined as the partial order $P = (F, \leq)$, where F is the set of faces of A and for $f_1, f_2 \in F$, $f_1 \leq f_2$ if and only if $f_1 \subseteq f_2$. A few authors have studied the dimension of such lattices. Reuter [22] determined the dimension of classic families of polytopes, such as simplices, cubes, prisms and bipyramids. Brightwell and Trotter [7] have concerned themselves with the dimension of polytopes in \mathbb{R}^3 .

One can extend this concept of the face lattice to arbitrary polyhedral complexes. Thus, this chapter was initially motivated by the following question. What is the dimension of the face order of a d -dimensional cube Grid? This question was initially proposed by Niklas Affolter, with a background in geometry, although he unfortunately did not recall why exactly he was interested in this result. As it turns out, answering this question will mainly involve a non-geometric approach.

A natural way to view a d -Grid is as a product of simple paths. In essence, let G_k be a path embedded into \mathbb{R} with vertices $\{0, \dots, k\}$ and edges $\{(i-1, i) \mid i \in \{1, \dots, k\}\}$. Then a d -dimensional Grid with side lengths k_1, \dots, k_d is given by the cartesian product $G_{k_1} \times \dots \times G_{k_d}$. This relationship also holds for the face order. Let F_k be the poset with elements $\{a_0, \dots, a_k\} \cup \{b_1, \dots, b_k\}$ and relations $a_i \leq b_j$ if $i \in \{j-1, j\}$, which is also commonly referred to as the k -Fence. Now the face order of G_k is given exactly by F_k . This relation also extends to grids, as the face order of a d -Grid with sides k_1, \dots, k_d is equal to $F_{k_1} \times \dots \times F_{k_d}$. Be aware that this only holds when we do not assign a minimal empty face to each cube of the grid. See Figure 3.1 for illustrating examples.

Figure 3.1.: One and two dimensional grids and their corresponding face orders.

To analyze the dimension of $F_{k_1} \times \dots \times F_{k_d}$, it is sensible to try and find upper and lower bounds for the dimension of $F \times P$ for any poset P , which we will provide in Section 3.1. Then in Section 3.2 we will use the methods we applied for Fence-Posets to also describe

an upper bound on Crown-Posets. We will also complete the proof of Theorem 1.7 we foreshadowed earlier.

3.1. Fence-Posets

Figure 3.2.: The k -fence F_k

Felsner and Mütze determined an upper bound for the dimension of $\dim(F \times P)$, if F is a fence and P is an arbitrary poset. We were provided a sketch of this proof and have in turn worked out the details. Felsner also mentioned that they believe that this upper bound constitutes a complete characterization of a class of fence-like posets. We will later see that essentially all of the constructions for the upper bound in this chapter also follow from a property which has already been discovered by Reuter in 1989. Nonetheless, we still wish to present this proof as it gives a nice introduction into the core ideas.

Proposition 3.1. *Let P be an arbitrary finite poset. Then, $\dim(P \times F_k) \leq \dim(P) + 1$.*

Proof. We will first define some new notation. For a sequence $L = p_1 \dots p_s$ of elements of P and a sequence $q_1 \dots q_t$ of elements we will define a sequence in $P \times Q$ by

$$L(q_1 \dots q_t) := (p_1, q_1) \dots (p_1, q_t)(p_2, q_1) \dots (p_2, q_t) \dots (p_s, q_1) \dots (p_s, q_t).$$

In other words, we take L and replace each p_i by $(p_i, q_1) \dots (p_i, q_t)$. Now let $R := \{L_1, \dots, L_k\}$ be a realizer of P . Define a new set of linear extensions R' of $P \times F_k$ by setting

$$\begin{aligned} L'_i &:= L_i(a_0 \dots a_d b_1 \dots b_d) \text{ for } 1 \leq i < k \\ L'_k &:= L_k(a_0) L_k(a_1 b_1) \dots L_k(a_d b_d) \\ L''_k &:= L_k(a_d) L_k(a_{d-1} b_d) \dots L_k(a_0 b_1). \end{aligned}$$

We claim that R' is a realizer of $P \times F_k$. Now consider a slightly modified definition of a realizer. A set of linear extensions R is a realizer if and only if for all $x, y \in P$ with $x \not\leq_P y$ there is some extension $L \in R$ such that $y <_L x$. This is a valid alternative characterization, because for incomparable x and y we have $x \not\leq y$ and $y \not\leq x$, so the pair is covered both ways. For x, y with $x < y$ it holds that $y \not\leq x$ and so $x <_L y$ because L is a linear extension.

Now let $(p, f), (\tilde{p}, \tilde{f}) \in P \times F_k$ with $(p, f) \not\leq (\tilde{p}, \tilde{f})$. Consider the cases:

- $f \not\leq \tilde{f}$: Then by construction it holds that either $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{f}) \not\leq_{L'_k} (p, f)$ or $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{f}) \not\leq_{L''_k} (p, f)$.

- $p \not\leq \tilde{p}$ and $f \leq \tilde{f}$: As $p \not\leq \tilde{p}$ there is some L_i such that $\tilde{p} <_{L_i} p$. If $i < k$ then $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{f}) <_{L_i} (p, f)$. So suppose $\tilde{p} <_{L_i} p$ is only true for $i = k$. By construction of L'_k and L''_k it must hold that $\tilde{L} = L_k(f\tilde{f})$ is contained in one of either L'_k or L''_k . Then within \tilde{L} we have $(\tilde{p}, \tilde{f}) \not\leq_{\tilde{L}} (p, f)$, so the pair is inverted.

Consequently R' is a realizer of $P \times F_k$ with $n + 1$ elements and thus $\dim(P \times F_k) \leq \dim(P) + 1$. \square

Take note of the core idea to form a block of the form $L(\dots a \dots b \dots)$ for all a, b with $a \leq b$. This will come up repeatedly.

To bound the dimension from below, we use another theorem by Reuter. Let V be the poset with elements $\{0, 1, 2\}$ and $0 \leq 1, 0 \leq 2$ and $1 \parallel 2$. Then

Theorem 3.2 ([22]). *Let P be a poset with $\mathbf{0}$. Then, $\dim(P \times V) = \dim(P) + 1$.*

This theorem has a nice geometric view. If P is the face lattice of a polytope with $\mathbf{0}$ but without $\mathbf{1}$, then $P \times V$ corresponds exactly to the face order of a bipyramid with base P without its maximal face.

Figure 3.3.: The face lattice of a bipyramid without $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$.

The original proof of this theorem makes heavy use of the concept of Ferrers dimension, which can be viewed as a generalization of order dimension. We have reformulated this proof so it does not require knowledge of this concept, although we will later reintroduce it in Chapter 4.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{0} \in P$ be the minimal element of P and let L_1, \dots, L_n be a realizer of $P \times V$. Let us first make some fundamental observations about $P \times V$. For $x, y \in P$ we have that $x \leq_P y$ if and only if $(x, 0) <_{P \times V} (y, 1)$. Define sets

$$\begin{aligned} I_0 &:= \{(x, y) \mid x, y \in P, ((x, 0), (y, 0)) \in \text{inc}(P \times V)\}, \\ I_1 &:= \{(x, y) \mid x, y \in P, ((x, 0), (y, 1)) \in \text{inc}(P \times V)\}, \\ I_2 &:= \{(x, y) \mid x, y \in P, ((x, 0), (y, 2)) \in \text{inc}(P \times V)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, subsets of I_0, I_1 or I_2 contain alternating cycles in $P \times V$ exactly if the corresponding projection onto pairs of P contains an alternating cycle. For $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} I_0^j &:= \{(x, y) \mid (x, y) \in I_0, (y, 0) <_{L_j} (x, 0)\}, \\ I_1^j &:= \{(x, y) \mid (x, y) \in I_1, (y, 1) <_{L_j} (x, 0)\}, \\ I_2^j &:= \{(x, y) \mid (x, y) \in I_2, (y, 2) <_{L_j} (x, 0)\}. \end{aligned}$$

So I_0^j, I_1^j and I_2^j are the set of pairs of I_0, I_1 and I_2 which have been inverted by L_j . Crucially, note that $I_1^j \cup I_2^j \subseteq I_0^j$, as $(x, y) \in I_1^j$ implies $(y, 1) <_{P \times V} (x, 0)$ and thus $(y, 0) <_{L_j} (y, 1) <_{L_j} (x, 0)$, so $I_1^j \subseteq I_0^j$. Analogous reasoning for I_2^j then also gives $I_2^j \subseteq I_0^j$.

Knowing this, the idea of the proof is to remove one of the L_j and modify the remaining L_j in such a way that I_0 will be completely covered by the remaining I_0^j . Projection then yields a smaller realizer of P . For $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ define $B_j := \{x \in P \mid (x, 2) <_{L_j} (\mathbf{0}, 1)\}$. Because $(\mathbf{0}, 1) \parallel (\mathbf{0}, 2)$ in $P \times V$, there is some $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $(\mathbf{0}, 1) <_{L_k} (\mathbf{0}, 2)$. With $(\mathbf{0}, 2) \leq (x, 2)$ for $x \in P$ it then follows that $B_k^2 = \emptyset$.

Now for $j \neq k$ let $\widehat{I}^j := I_1^j \cup ((P \times B_j) \cap I_1^k)$. We will show that $\bigcup_{j \neq k} \widehat{I}^j = \text{inc}(P)$ and that each \widehat{I}^j contains no alternating cycle of P , which will imply that we can find $n - 1$ linear extensions each inverting the pairs in one \widehat{I}^j , thus forming a realizer. Then it must hold that $\dim(P) \leq n - 1$ and the theorem follows.

To show that \widehat{I}^j is cycle free, note that none of I_1^j and I_1^k contain an alternating cycle. Thus any alternating cycle must cross between the sets I_1^j and $(P \times B_j) \cap I_1^k$. But this is not possible as $y_b \in B_j$ and $(x_1, y_1) \in I_1^j$ implies

$$(y_b, 0) <_{L_j} (y_b, 2) \leq_{L_j} (0, 1) \leq_{L_j} (y_1, 1) <_{L_j} (x_1, 0),$$

so $x_1 \not\leq_P y_b$ and therefore edges in the cycle graph cannot cross from I_1^j to B_j .

Finally, proving that $\bigcup_{j \neq k} \widehat{I}^j = \text{inc}(P)$ is not difficult. Note that $\bigcup_{j=1}^n B_j = P$, because for any $x, y \in P$ we get $(x, 1) \parallel (y, 2)$ and the L_i form a realizer. But recall that k was chosen such that $B_k = \emptyset$, so $\bigcup_{j \neq k} B_j = P$ and thus $\bigcup_{j \neq k} (P \times B_j) \cap I_1^k = I_1^k$. Therefore

$$\bigcup_{j \neq k} \widehat{I}^j = \bigcup_{j \neq k} I_1^j \cup ((P \times B_j) \cap I_1^k) = \left(\bigcup_{j \neq k} I_1^j \right) \cup I_1^k = \bigcup_{j=1}^n I_1^j = \text{inc}(P),$$

where the last equality follows as the L_j form a realizer and thus $I_1 = \text{inc}(P)$ must be covered by the I_1^j . \square

We can modify the assumption that P must have a minimal element by adding them during the construction. For $P = (X, \leq_P)$, we define $B(P) = (X_0 \cup X_1 \cup X_2 \cup \{l_1, l_2\}, \leq_{B(P)})$ to be the poset consisting of three copies of P and two additional elements l_1, l_2 , with $l_1 \leq x$ if and only if $x \in X_1$ and similarly $l_2 \leq x$ if and only if $x \in X_2$. Also for $x_0 \in X_0, y_1 \in X_1$ set $x_0 \leq y_1$ if for the corresponding elements of X , $x \leq y$. Similarly for $x_0 \in X_0, y_2 \in X_2$ set $x_0 \leq y_2$ if $x \leq y$. This is a bipyramid construction for posets without $\mathbf{0}$. We then get a straightforward corollary.

Corollary 3.3. *Let P be an arbitrary poset. Then, $\dim(B(P)) = \dim(P) + 1$.*

Proof. Let \tilde{P} be the poset acquired by adding $\mathbf{0}$ to P . Then $B(P)$ is isomorphic to $\tilde{P} \times V$ without $\mathbf{0}$. The statement now follows from $\dim(P) = \dim(\tilde{P})$. \square

By “flipping” posets – that is, exchanging \leq with \geq – the last two results also apply to F_1 , which is just a flipped V , and a poset P with $\mathbf{1}$. The map $B(P)$ then translates from a bipyramid to a prism construction. We can now determine the dimension of the face lattice of the d -dimensional hypercube by using that the face lattice of the cube without $\mathbf{1}$ is isomorphic to the d -times product of F_1 .

Corollary 3.4 ([22]). *Let H_d be the face lattice of the d -dimensional hypercube. Then $\dim(H_d) = d + 1$.*

We can now apply these results to our representation mentioned at the beginning of this chapter to determine the dimension of the grid.

Corollary 3.5. *The dimension of the face order of a d -Grid with side-lengths k_1, \dots, k_d , $k_i \geq 1$ is equal to $d + 1$.*

Proof. As $\dim(F_k) = 2$, repeated application of Proposition 3.1 implies that the order dimension of the d -Grid is at most $d + 1$. The face order of the d -dimensional hypercube is given by F_2^d and Theorem 3.2 implies that $\dim(F_2^d) = d + 1$. Now monotonicity of dimension implies that the dimension of the d -Grid is at least, and thus exactly $d + 1$. \square

3.1.1. Characterizing Fences

Felsner also outlined how to extend the ideas from Proposition 3.1 to an entire class of posets. We call a poset P an *extended fence* if the cover graph of P is a path.

Figure 3.4.: An extended fence F .

Consider the given poset F in Figure 3.4. Then for an arbitrary poset P , it holds that $\dim(P \times F) \leq \dim(P) + 1$. For a realizer L_1, \dots, L_k of P let $L := L_k$. We can construct a realizer of $P \times F$ in by setting

$$\begin{aligned} L'_i &:= L_i(1 \dots 13) \text{ for } 1 \leq i < k \\ L'_k &:= L(1)L(2)L(3)L(6\ 5\ 4)L(10\ 9\ 8\ 7)L(11)L(12) \\ L''_k &:= L(10\ 11\ 12)L(9)L(8)L(6\ 7)L(5)L(1\ 2\ 3\ 4). \end{aligned}$$

The similarities to the proof of Proposition 3.1 should be apparent. Instead of putting just one comparable pair into a block of L , we have now added an entire maximal chain

into one such block. To convince oneself that this is a realizer, it is best to check similar conditions as in the proof of Proposition 3.1. In essence, for each pair $x, y \in F$ with $x \leq_F y$ we can find a block $L(x \dots y)$ in L'_k or L''_k , while for each pair $x, y \in F$ with $x \not\leq_F y$, we find $L(\dots y \dots)L(\dots x \dots)$ in L'_k or L''_k .

More generally, view an arbitrary extended fence F via its cover graph with its edges being marked by “up” or “down” respectively. Be aware that the minimal size 2 realizer for an extended fence is unique. The first extension is given by always choosing the leftmost minimal element in a diagram in sequence and the second extension is obtained by picking the rightmost minimal elements. Constructing the realizer of $F \times P$ is now done by forming L -blocks around consecutive maximal sequences of “down-edges” in L'_k when going left-to-right and consecutive sequences of “up-edges” in L''_k when going right-to-left.

Lemma 3.6. *Let F be an extended fence and P be an arbitrary poset. Then $\dim(P \times F) \leq \dim(P) + 1$.*

It turns out that the converse of this statement is also true. That is, if for a fixed poset F , $\dim(P \times F) \leq \dim(P) + 1$ for all finite posets P , then F is a disjoint union of extended fences. The easiest way to check this is to find counter examples for all posets P whose cover graph is not a path. This means that the cover graph either has a vertex of degree three or contains a cycle. Now, by monotonicity of dimension and the natural symmetries obtained by replacing \leq with \geq , it is enough to find examples for the four types of posets listed in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5.: If P is not an extended Fence, it contains one of these posets.

Let us go through all of the cases in sequence. The cases for B_2 and C_k for $k \geq 3$ are easily handled. As mentioned in Section 1.2, $B_2 \times B_2 \cong B_4$, so

$$\dim(B_2 \times B_2) = \dim(B_4) = 4 > 3 = \dim(B_2) + 1.$$

For $k \geq 3$, note that $\dim(C_d) \geq 3$. See Section 3.2 for a proof. Thus for any chain L , we get $\dim(L \times C_d) \geq 3 > 2 = \dim(L) + 1$. The other cases are more involved. Although one could just prove the next results by computer search, we still elect to prove these statements by hand. Reuter has shown that $\dim(Z_3 \times Z_3) = 4 > \dim(Z_3) + 1 = 3$. We give a conceptually similar proof here.

Lemma 3.7 ([21]). $\dim(Z_3 \times Z_3) = \dim(Z_3) + \dim(Z_3) = 4$.

Proof. Start by describing the critical pairs of $Z_3 \times Z_3$. To do this, note that $Z_3 \times Z_3$ consists of three “layers”. $S_H = \{a, b, c\} \times \{a, b, c\}$, $S_L = \{a, b, c\} \times \{0\} \cup \{0\} \times \{a, b, c\}$ and $\{(0, 0)\}$. $\{(0, 0)\}$ is the unique minimum of $Z_3 \times Z_3$, so it does not contribute to dimension.

It is now not difficult to see that $\text{crit}(P) = S_L \times S_H \cap \text{inc}(P)$. That is, the critical pairs are exactly those incomparabilities between S_L and S_H . Suppose $\dim(Z_3 \times Z_3) = 3$ and let L_1, L_2, L_3 form a realizer. We will prove the statement via case distinction on the maximal elements of L_1, L_2 and L_3 and show that they cannot cover all critical pairs. We denote the maximum of L_i restricted to S_L by S_L^i .

Due to symmetries we may assume that one of three cases is true.

- Case 1: $S_L^1 = (a, 0), S_L^2 = (a, 0)$,
- Case 2: $S_L^1 = (a, 0), S_L^2 = (b, 0), S_L^3 = (c, 0)$,
- Case 3: $S_L^1 = (a, 0), S_L^2 = (b, 0), S_L^3 = (0, c)$.

In Case 1 we have $(0, c) < (a, 0) < (a, b)$ in L_1 and L_2 . Therefore in L_3 we must have $(0, b) < (a, b) < (0, c) < (a, c)$. But then $((0, b), (a, c))$ has never been inverted, since in L_1 and L_2 we also have $(0, b) < (a, 0) < (a, c)$ by assumption.

For Case 2 we may assume, without loss of generality, that $(0, a) < (0, b) < (0, c) < (a, 0)$ in L_1 . Then in L_1 we have $(0, a) < (0, c) < (b, c)$ and in L_2 we get $(0, a) < (b, 0) < (b, c)$. Hence, in L_3 we must have $(0, c) < (b, c) < (0, a) < (a, a)$. For L_1 one also has $(0, a) < (0, c) < (c, c)$ and in L_3 it must be that $(0, a) < (c, 0) < (c, c)$. Thus, it must be that $(0, c) < (c, c) < (0, a) < (a, a)$ in L_2 . But now $(0, c) < (a, a)$ in L_2, L_3 and – by assumption for Case 2 – L_1 , so this pair has not been inverted.

We split Case 3 into two more instances. First suppose $(0, a) < (c, 0)$ and $(0, b) < (c, 0)$ in L_3 . Then we may also assume, without loss of generality, $(0, a) < (0, b)$ in L_3 . It follows that $(0, a) < (a, b)$ in L_3 and $(0, a) < (a, b)$ in L_1 by assumption. So $(0, b) < (a, b) < (0, a) < (c, a)$ must be true in L_2 . Similarly one gets $(0, a) < (b, b)$ in both L_2 and L_3 , so $(0, b) < (b, b) < (0, a) < (c, a)$ in L_1 . By Case 3 now $(0, b) < (c, 0) < (c, a)$ in L_3 , so $(0, b), (c, a)$ has not been inverted.

Finally, suppose Case 3 and one of $(c, 0) < (0, a)$ or $(c, 0) < (0, b)$ in L_3 to be true. We just check $(c, 0) < (0, a)$ in L_3 , as the other case is similar. Now we have $(c, 0) < (a, a)$ in L_3 and L_1 , so $(0, a) < (a, a) < (c, 0) < (c, c)$ in L_2 . Also $(c, 0) < (b, a)$ in L_3 and L_2 , thus $(0, a) < (b, a) < (c, 0) < (c, c)$ in L_1 . Now, because $(0, c)$ was last in L_1 , the pair $(0, a), (c, c)$ has not been inverted.

Since all cases lead to a contradiction, a size 3 realizer of $Z_3 \times Z_3$ does not exist. \square

To handle the remaining cases, we have found a 4-irreducible poset, which $Y \times Y$ and $C_2 \times C_2$ have in common. It belongs to a family of posets, that are constructed by adding two new minimal vertices to a $2n$ -Crown. The family is formally defined as follows. Define the poset by $P_n := (X_n, \leq_n)$, where

$$X_n := \{l_1, l_2\} \cup \{a_1, \dots, a_{2n}\} \cup \{b_1, \dots, b_{2n}\}$$

and for comparabilities

$$\begin{aligned} l_1 &\leq_n a_i \text{ if } i \text{ is odd,} \\ l_2 &\leq_n a_i \text{ if } i \text{ is even,} \\ a_i &\leq_n b_j \text{ if } j \in \{i, i+1\} \text{ (cyclically).} \end{aligned}$$

Due to transitivity, this also implies $l_s \leq b_i$ for all $s \in \{1, 2\}, i \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}$.

Figure 3.6.: The poset P_n .

Lemma 3.8. *For $n \geq 2$ P_n is a 4-irreducible poset.*

Proof. Let us start by defining sets for each “layer” of P_n . So let $S_l = \{l_1, l_2\}$, $S_a = \{a_1, \dots, a_{2n}\}$ and $S_b = \{b_1, \dots, b_{2n}\}$. The critical pairs of P_n are now exactly given by the incomparable pairs $D := \text{inc}(P) \cap (S_l \times S_a)$ and $U := \text{inc}(P) \cap (S_a \times S_b)$. So $\text{crit}(P) = D \cup U$. An immediate fact about D is, that each $(l, a) \in D$ must involve either l_1 or l_2 . So split $D = D_1 \dot{\cup} D_2$ into just the pairs involving l_1 or l_2 . Because the minimal element of any linear extension must be either l_1 or l_2 , it is not possible to invert a pair in D_1 and a pair in D_2 at the same time.

Now suppose there exist linear extensions L_1, L_2, L_3 forming a realizer of P_n . The observation above implies that one of these extensions must invert all pairs of either D_1 or D_2 . Without loss of generality, let this extension be L_1 and the inverted pairs be all pairs in D_1 . Because now $a_{2k} <_{L_1} l_1 <_{L_1} b_l$ for all $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}, l \in \{1, \dots, 2n\}$, this means none of the pairs in U involving any a_{2k} have been covered by L_1 . There is also at least one $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that no pair of U involving a_{2i-1} is covered, as each b is larger than one odd and one even a and one odd a has to be taken first. Observe that there must be an extension covering (l_2, a_{2i-1}) . Let this be L_2 . Now, no pairs of U involving a_{2i-1} are covered in L_1 or L_2 . Similarly to a_{2i-1} , there is also some $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that no pairs in U involving a_{2j} are covered in L_2 . Thus in L_1 and L_2 , none of the pairs in U involving a_{2i-1} and a_{2j} have been covered. But L_3 cannot cover all pairs with these

two elements, because there are $\widehat{b}_i, \widehat{b}_j$ such that the four elements $a_{2i-1}, a_{2j}, \widehat{b}_i, \widehat{b}_j$ form the standard example S_2 , which requires two additional extensions. Thus $\dim(P_n) \geq 4$.

To see that $\dim(P_n) \leq 4$, we can define a realizer by

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= l_1 a_1 a_3 \dots a_{2n-1} l_2 a_2 b_2 b_3 a_4 b_4 b_5 \dots a_{2n} b_{2n} b_1, \\ L_2 &= l_1 a_1 a_3 \dots a_{2n-1} l_2 a_{2n} b_{2n} b_1 a_{2n-2} b_{2n-2} b_{2n-1} \dots a_2 b_2 b_3, \\ L_3 &= l_2 a_2 a_4 \dots a_{2n} l_1 a_1 b_1 b_2 a_3 b_3 b_4 \dots a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} b_{2n}, \\ L_4 &= l_2 a_2 a_4 \dots a_{2n} l_1 a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} b_{2n} a_{2n-3} b_{2n-3} b_{2n-2} \dots a_1 b_1 b_2. \end{aligned}$$

To see that this is a realizer, convince yourself that after removing l_1, l_2 and all even a or all odd a , we are left with an n -times disjoint union of the V poset, which has dimension 2. So if we take all of the odd a and then l_2 , we can use two extensions to cover all pairs in U involving even a and all pairs in D_1 . Repeat the same but with exchanged parities to build a realizer.

To show that this poset is indeed irreducible, because of the symmetries of P_n it suffices to show that $\dim(P - l_1) = \dim(P - a_1) = \dim(P - b_1) = 3$. A realizer after removing l_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= a_1 a_2 \dots a_{2n-1} l_2 a_2 b_2 b_3 a_4 b_4 b_5 \dots a_{2n} b_{2n} b_1, \\ L_2 &= l_2 a_{2n} a_1 b_1 a_2 b_2 \dots a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} b_{2n}, \\ L_3 &= l_2 a_{2n} a_{2n-1} b_{2n} a_{2n-2} b_{2n-1} \dots a_1 b_1 b_2. \end{aligned}$$

After removing a_1 , a realizer is

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= l_1 a_3 a_5 \dots a_{2n-1} l_2 a_2 b_2 b_3 a_4 b_4 b_5 \dots a_{2n} b_{2n} b_1, \\ L_2 &= l_2 a_2 a_4 \dots a_{2n} l_1 b_1 b_2 a_3 b_3 b_4 a_5 b_5 b_6 \dots a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} b_{2n}, \\ L_3 &= l_1 l_2 a_{2n} b_1 a_{2n-1} b_{2n} \dots a_2 b_3 b_2. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, a realizer after removing b_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= l_1 a_1 a_3 \dots a_{2n-1} l_2 a_2 b_3 b_3 a_4 b_4 b_5 \dots a_{2n} b_{2n}, \\ L_2 &= l_2 a_2 a_4 \dots a_{2n} l_1 a_1 b_2 a_3 b_3 b_4 \dots a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} b_{2n}, \\ L_3 &= l_1 l_2 a_{2n} a_{2n-1} b_{2n} a_{2n-1} b_{2n-1} \dots a_2 b_3 a_1 b_2. \end{aligned}$$

The basic idea behind these realizers is that, after removing all odd or even a , one is left with a disjoint union of V posets, which in general only require two extensions to cover. \square

Proposition 3.9. *Let C_2 be the 2-Crown and Y be the poset depicted in Figure 3.5. Then $\dim(C_2 \times C_2) = \dim(Y \times Y) = 4$.*

Figure 3.7.: P_2 in $C_2 \times C_2$ and $Y \times Y$

Proof. See Figure 3.7 for a sketch. Let

$$P_{C_2} = \left\{ (a_1, a_1), (a_2, a_2), (a_1, b_1), (a_1, b_2), (b_1, a_2), (b_2, a_2), \right. \\ \left. (b_1, b_1), (b_1, b_2), (b_2, b_1), (b_2, b_2) \right\}.$$

and

$$P_Y = \left\{ (b, a), (c_1, a), (c_2, a), (a, b), (a, c_1), (c_1, c_1), (c_2, c_1), (a, c_2), (c_1, c_2), (c_2, c_2) \right\}$$

The induced subposets of Y with regards to P_Y and C_2 with regards to P_{C_2} are then isomorphic to P_2 . The statement then follows by monotonicity of dimension. \square

Having verified all the cases the main theorem is now immediate.

Theorem 3.10. *Let P be a finite poset. Then the cover graph of P is a disjoint union of paths if and only if $\dim(Q \times P) \leq \dim(Q) + 1$ for all finite posets Q .*

This gives a nice characterization of extended fences, but the proof of this does not immediately reveal any deeper insights on the product of orders, since we just find counter examples for all other posets. Still, this theorem positions extended fences as, in a way, uniquely low-dimensional among 2-dimensional posets. This is, if nothing else, intuitive and ultimately what one would hope to be the case.

3.2. Crown-Posets

The critical reader may point out that the counter examples given for the Crown C_k with $k \geq 3$ in Subsection 3.1.1 are quite trivial. It turns out that during our search

for counterexamples we were unable to find more illuminating examples by hand or by computer search. The reason for this is that, perhaps surprisingly, non-trivial examples do not exist. In essence, there is no poset P with $\dim(P) \geq 2$ such that $\dim(P \times C_k) \geq \dim(P) + 1$. The proof of this will employ similar methods as the proof of Proposition 3.1 and, except for the one dimensional case, generalizes Proposition 3.1, as any fence is contained within a large enough crown.

To start with, we formally define the k -Crown as the poset $C_k = (X, \leq)$ with $X = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \cup \{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$. Set $a_i \leq b_j$ if $j \in \{i, i+1\}$, where indices are viewed cyclically. As mentioned earlier, $\dim(C_k) = 3$ for $n \geq 3$. To convince oneself of this, suppose $\dim(C_k) = 2$ and let L_1, L_2 be a realizer of C_k . Let $A := \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$. Note that the two smallest elements of L_1 must be elements of A , as every element in $B := \{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$ has two elements smaller than itself. So without loss of generality let a_1, a_2 be the two smallest elements of L_1 . As a_1 is minimal in L_1 , none of the pairs $\{(a_1, x) : x \in P, x \parallel a_1\}$ have been inverted. Therefore, L_2 restricted to $\{a_1 \dots a_k\}$ must have a_1 as its maximum. This gives $a_2 <_{L_1} b_1$ and $a_2 <_{L_2} a_1 <_{L_2} b_1$ but a_2 and b_1 are incomparable and have not been inverted, which is a contradiction.

Be aware that size 3 realizers of C_k are, unlike fences, not unique. One such realizer, for example, is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= a_1 a_k b_1 a_2 \dots a_{k-1} b_2 \dots b_k, \\ L_2 &= a_1 a_2 b_2 a_3 b_3 a_4 b_4 \dots a_k b_k b_1, \\ L_3 &= a_k a_{k-1} b_k a_{k-2} b_{k-1} \dots a_2 b_3 a_1 b_2 b_1. \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

With these preliminaries established, we can now prove the theorem.

Theorem 3.11. *Let P be a finite poset and $k \geq 3$. Then,*

$$\dim(P \times C_k) \leq \max(3, \dim(P) + 1).$$

Proof. Of course, $P \times C_k$ contains C_k , so $\dim(P \times C_k) \geq 3$. If $\dim(P) = 1$, just set $L_{n-1} = L_n = P$ in the following construction. Let $n = \dim(P) \geq 3$ and L_1, \dots, L_n be a realizer of P . We define a realizer of $P \times C_k$ via the linear extensions

$$\begin{aligned} L'_i &:= L_i(a_1 \dots a_k b_1 \dots b_k) \text{ for } 1 \leq i < n-1, \\ L'_{n-1} &:= L_n(a_1 a_k b_1) L_{n-1}(a_2 \dots a_{k-1} b_2 \dots b_k), \\ L'_n &:= L_n(a_1 a_2 b_2) L_n(a_3 b_3) \dots L_{n-1}(a_k b_k b_1), \\ L''_n &:= L_n(a_k a_{k-1} b_k) L_n(a_{k-2} b_{k-1}) \dots L_{n-1}(a_1 b_2 b_1). \end{aligned}$$

To show that this is a realizer let $(p, c) \not\leq (\tilde{p}, \tilde{c})$ in $P \times C_k$ similar to the proof of Proposition 3.1. Consider the two following cases.

- $c \not\leq \tilde{c}$: If $\tilde{c} \neq \{b_1, a_1, a_k\}$, then the pair is inverted in either L'_n or L''_n . If $\tilde{c} = b_1$, then the pair is inverted in L'_{n-1} . For $\tilde{c} = a_1$ and $c \neq a_2$, the pair is inverted in L'_n and for $c = a_2$ it is inverted in L'_{n-1} with analogous reasoning for $\tilde{c} = a_k$ and $c = a_2$ or $c \neq a_2$ but with L''_n instead of L'_n .

- $p \not\leq \tilde{p}$ and $c \leq \tilde{c}$: As $p \not\leq \tilde{p}$, there is some $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $\tilde{p} <_{L_i} p$. If $i < n - 1$, then the desired pair is inverted in L'_i . If $i = n - 1$ and $c \notin \{a_1, a_k\}$, then the pair is inverted in $L_{n-1}(a_2 \dots a_{k-1} b_2 \dots b_k)$. If $c = a_1$ or $c = a_k$, then the part $L_{n-1}(a_1 b_2 b_1)$ of L''_n or the part $L_{n-1}(a_k b_k b_1)$ of L'_n respectively suffices. Lastly, if $i = n$ and $c \in \{a_1, a_k\}$, then one of the blocks $L_n(a_1 a_k b_1)$, $L_n(a_1 a_2 b_2)$ or $L_n(a_k a_{k-1} b_k)$ will invert the pair. For all $c \notin \{a_1, a_k\}$ with $c \leq \tilde{c}$ one of L'_n or L''_n contains $L_n(c\tilde{c})$, where the pair is inverted, as a subextension. □

We can generalize the above theorem to “extended crowns”, similarly to Lemma 3.6 by replacing comparable pairs with longer chains in the construction. This also shows that, at least for products, the crowns are only weakly 3-dimensional. The realizer we gave in (3.1) is also an indication of this, as it has a unusually high degree of freedom in L_1 . We tried of course, but were unable to find any posets with $\dim(P \times C_k) = \dim(P)$, but we do also believe that this is not possible. A good indication of this is that even although we just claimed that C_k is only barely 3-dimensional we still get $\dim(C_k \times C_l) = 4$ for $k, l \geq 3$. This means that there is no way to meaningfully exploit the ideas from the upper bound for both crowns to get an even stronger bound.

Proposition 3.12. $\dim(C_k \times C_l) = 4$, for $k, l \geq 3$.

Proof. The upper bound immediately follows from Theorem 3.11. For the lower bound we will show that subposet of C_k formed between the top and the bottom layer already has dimension 4.

Let L be a linear extension of $C_k \times C_l$ and without loss of generality let (b_1, b_1) be the smallest element from the top layer in L . So suppose the first element of $\{b_1, \dots, b_k\} \times \{b_1, \dots, b_l\}$ in L is (b_1, b_1) . Recognize that all elements smaller than (b_1, b_1) are given by

$$D(b_1, b_1) = \{(a_1, a_1), (a_1, a_l), (a_k, a_1), (a_k, a_l)\}.$$

Because (b_1, b_1) is first among the (b_i, b_j) in L , none of the critical pairs involving any of the elements in $D(b_1, b_1)$ have been inverted in L . But now recognize that the induced poset of $\{(b_1, b_2), (b_2, b_1), (b_1, b_l), (b_k, b_1)\} \cup D(b_1, b_1)$ forms a 4-crown (see Figure 3.8), and we just showed that none of its critical pairs have been inverted yet. Hence we need at least three more linear extensions to construct a realizer. □

Figure 3.8.: 4-crown blocked by (b_1, b_1)

To conclude this chapter, let us briefly return to Theorem 1.7, as we have collected all of the ingredients of the proof by now. In order to prove that $\dim(P \times P) \geq 4$ for any 3-dimensional poset P , it is enough to just consider 3-irreducible posets, as each 3-dimensional poset contains some 3-irreducible poset. To prove this, examine the list of 3-irreducible posets by Kelly [17] or Trotter and Moore [26, pp. 62-66], who have both enumerated all 3-irreducible posets. Going through the list of posets, all of them except for the Chevron or the crowns contain a copy of Z_3 . And as we have shown in Lemma 3.7, $\dim(Z_3 \times Z_3) = 4$, so $\dim(P \times P) \geq 4$ for these posets. Therefore we just need to check the Chevron and the crowns separately. Note that the Chevron contains a copy of C_2 , and $\dim(C_2 \times C_2) = 4$ according to Proposition 3.9. We have handled the case of the crowns in Proposition 3.12, thus the proof is complete.

Figure 3.9.: C_2 inside the Chevron and Z_3 inside a 3-irreducible poset

While this result is ostensibly nice to have, it does not provide any general methods for calculating lower bounds for the dimension of products. Furthermore, it is likely the case that an argument by such an enumeration is entirely unviable for 4-dimensional posets. As Trotter himself says [26, p. 102]:

3-irreducible posets are well behaved and especially rare. For $t \geq 4$,
 t -irreducible posets are arbitrarily bizarre and surprisingly abundant.

Clearly, finding such lower bounds in general requires much deeper insights about the product, which just have not been found yet.

4. The Covering Property

After establishing the results in the last chapter, we noticed during our research that Reuter [21] already mentioned a property which, according to an easily overlooked sidenote of his, implies Theorem 3.11. We will see that this property encompasses the core ideas of Proposition 3.1 and Theorem 3.11 by describing a condition for P that yields upper bounds on $\dim(P \times Q)$ for all posets Q . The original description of this mainly relies on the concept of Ferrers dimension, a generalization of order dimension that can sometimes be unwieldy and overly technical. This is not helped by the fact that Reuters original description is somewhat sparse. We have thus defined an equivalent property directly on partial orders, which should be easier to understand and integrates nicely with our previous results.

We start with introducing the concept of Ferrers dimension and repeating the original proof before giving the alternative formulation.

4.1. Introducing Ferrers Relations

Ferrers Relations were first formally introduced and named by Riguet [23] in an algebraic context, although fundamentally they arose even earlier in the field of mathematical psychology in a work by Guttman [15]. They were then later also referred to as “biorders” by Doignon, Ducamp, and Falmagne [9]. In this chapter, we will work with the definition of a Ferrers Relation as is common in Formal Concept Analysis [13].

Let G, M be finite sets and $I \subseteq G \times M$ be a relation between these two sets. The triple (G, M, I) is called a *context*. A relation $F \subseteq G \times M$ is a *Ferrers Relation*, if for $g_1, g_2 \in G$ and $m_1, m_2 \in M$ we get

$$(g_1, m_1) \in F \text{ and } (g_2, m_2) \in F \implies (g_1, m_2) \in F \text{ or } (g_2, m_1) \in F.$$

A common way to visualize a context and a relation is within a table. If we index the rows and columns by G and M respectively and mark $(g, m) \in F$ with a cross, then a Ferrers Relation is a relation which contains no $\begin{smallmatrix} \times & \\ & \times \end{smallmatrix}$ or $\begin{smallmatrix} & \times \\ \times & \end{smallmatrix}$ subtable. The *Ferrers dimension* of a context $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I)$ is now defined as the smallest t , such that I is the intersection of t Ferrers Relations. This is well defined as $G \times M \setminus \{(g, m)\}$ is always a Ferrers Relation for any $(g, m) \in G \times M$. We will henceforth denote the Ferrers dimension of a context \mathbb{K} by $\text{fdim}(\mathbb{K})$.

Because the complement of $\begin{smallmatrix} \times & \\ & \times \end{smallmatrix}$ is $\begin{smallmatrix} & \times \\ \times & \end{smallmatrix}$, the complement $G \times M \setminus F$ of a Ferrers Relation F is also a Ferrers Relation. This means that the Ferrers dimension of $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I)$ is also

the smallest t , such that $G \times M \setminus I$ is the union of t Ferrers Relations. This formulation has the advantage of often being easy to visualize, as we can represent the context \mathbb{K} as well as the Ferrers Relations that cover $G \times M \setminus I$ in a table. See Figure 4.1 for an example. Therefore, we define a *representation* of a context \mathbb{K} , to be a set of Ferrers Relations F_1, \dots, F_t , such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^t F_i = G \times M \setminus I$.

×	×	1	1	1
2	×	×	1	1
2	2	×	×	1
2	2	2	×	×
×	3	3	3	×

Figure 4.1.: A context and its representation. \times represents elements of I . Number i represents elements of a Ferrers Relation $F_i \subseteq G \times M \setminus I$.

The primary reason why Ferrers Relations are of interest to us is due to a result attributed to Bouchet [6].

Theorem 4.1 ([6]). *Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a partial order. Then for the induced context $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, \leq)$ it holds that $\dim(P) = \text{fdim}(\mathbb{K})$.*

The original proof of Bouchet involves a detour via the Dedekind-MacNeille completion. Ganter [12] provides a modern reference for the underlying ideas. Cogis [8] also gave a more compact direct proof of the theorem by showing that minimal Ferrers Relations containing a partial order are total orders. Our proof will show a clear connection between Ferrers Relations and alternating cycles. We arrived at it independently although we later noticed that this idea has also been described by Doignon, Ducamp, and Falmagne [9]. First note that we can strengthen the definition of a Ferrers Relation in an intuitive way.

Lemma 4.2. *$F \subseteq G \times M$ is a Ferrers Relation if and only if all for $k \geq 2$, F contains no sequence $(g_1, m_1), \dots, (g_k, m_k) \in F$ where $(g_i, m_{i+1}) \notin F$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$, with $m_{k+1} := m_1$.*

Proof. The backwards direction is trivial, as $k = 2$ exactly means that there is no $\begin{smallmatrix} \times \\ \times \end{smallmatrix}$ or $\begin{smallmatrix} \times \\ \times \end{smallmatrix}$. For the other direction, a sketch is given in Figure 4.2. We will show via inductive reasoning that F contains no $(g_1, m_1), \dots, (g_k, m_k) \in F$ with $(g_i, m_{i+1}) \notin F$ for all i . Suppose such a sequence exists in F . Then (g_k, m_1) and (g_{k-1}, m_k) are not contained in F . Because the complement of a Ferrers Relation is also a Ferrers Relation, one of (g_k, m_k) or (g_{k-1}, m_1) must also not be contained in F . By assumption this must be (g_{k-1}, m_1) . Now repeat this argument for the sequence $(g_1, m_1), \dots, (g_{k-1}, m_{k-1})$ until we get that (g_2, m_1) is not contained in F . Now, $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2) \in F$ but $(g_1, m_2), (g_2, m_1) \notin F$, which contradicts the assumption that F is a Ferrers Relation. \square

The definition of the forbidden sequences in Lemma 4.2 is very similar to the definition of an alternating cycle for partial orders. More so, let $P = (X, I)$ be a poset and $S \subseteq \text{inc}(P)$.

Figure 4.2.: Sketch of Lemma 4.2. \times represents $(g, m) \in F$. \circ represents $(g, m) \notin F$.

S can only be part of a Ferrers Relation in $F \subseteq X \times X \setminus I$ if it contains no alternating cycle, as $(x, y_{i+1}) \in I$ implies $(x, y_{i+1}) \notin F$ and this contradicts Lemma 4.2. With this observation the proof of Theorem 4.1 follows.

Proof of Theorem 4.1. Let $P = (X, I)$ be a finite poset and let $F \subseteq X \times X \setminus I$ be a Ferrers Relation. To see that $\text{fdim}(\mathbb{K}) \leq \dim(P)$, observe that for every linear extension L of P , the set $F_L = \{(x, y) \in X \times X \mid y <_L x\}$ is a Ferrers Relation in $X \times X \setminus I$. This is easy to see as F_L forms the lower triangle of the table of \mathbb{K} after appropriate reordering of rows and columns. In particular, for a realizer L_1, \dots, L_k of P , the sets F_{L_1}, \dots, F_{L_k} form a representation of \mathbb{K} , as all $(x, y) \in \text{inc}(P)$ are covered since the L_i form a realizer and all (x, y) with $y <_P x$ must be covered in each F_{L_i} .

To prove $\dim(P) \leq \text{fdim}(\mathbb{K})$ let F_1, \dots, F_k be a representation of \mathbb{K} . Then by Lemma 4.2, the sets $F_k \cap \text{inc}(P)$ do not contain alternating cycles. Now applying Fact 1.2 yields that there is a linear extension L_i which reverses all pairs in $F_i \cap \text{inc}(P)$ and because $\bigcup_{i=1}^k F_k = X \times X \setminus I \supseteq \text{inc}(P)$, the extensions L_1, \dots, L_k form a realizer. \square

In general, when trying to transfer proofs and concepts from the realm of Ferrers relations to partial orders, we found it best to think of a Ferrers relation $F \in G \times M \setminus I$ as a set of pairs inverted by some linear extension L .

Theorem 4.1 shows that Ferrers dimension is a strict generalization of order dimension. In addition for a poset $P = (X, I)$, this proof positions Ferrers Relations of $X \times X \setminus I$ right in-between linear extensions and subsets without alternating cycles, in the sense that they have less structure than linear extensions but more structure than a cycle free subset. This comes in handy when one needs to highlight specifically which pairs one wants to invert, while still maintaining more structure.

That said, drawing tables as a visual representation of Ferrers dimension can quickly become unwieldy, even for posets of modest size. There is a way to reduce the size of context while maintaining dimension, with core ideas similar to those behind critical pairs, but we refrain from covering the details here. Suffice it to say that if the drawing of a table does not include a row and column for every element, then we have applied this reduction. For more details see [21].

4.2. Upper Bounds via Coverings

In this section we will repeat the original proof by Reuter of the covering property to determine upper bounds on products, describe our reformulation and finally provide some illustrating examples. We hope to provide an easy to understand view of what makes the theorem work in this section.

4.2.1. Covering Ferrers Relations

Similar to partial orders, there is also a cartesian product on contexts. For contexts $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I_{\mathbb{K}})$ and $\mathbb{L} = (H, N, I_{\mathbb{L}})$, the product $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$ is defined, as $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L} := (G \times H, M \times N, I)$, where $I = \{((g, h), (m, n)) \in (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \mid (g, m) \in I_{\mathbb{K}}, (h, n) \in I_{\mathbb{L}}\}$. Clearly the induced context of the product of posets P and Q is equal to the product of the induced contexts, hence examining the products of contexts is justified for our purposes. Crucially, one can lift Fact 1.4 to the Ferrers Dimension of concepts.

Fact 4.3 ([21]). Let $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I_{\mathbb{K}})$, $\mathbb{L} = (H, N, I_{\mathbb{L}})$ be contexts. Then

$$\text{fdim}(\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}) \leq \text{fdim}(\mathbb{K}) + \text{fdim}(\mathbb{L}).$$

Proof. Let E_1, \dots, E_n be a representation of \mathbb{K} and F_1, \dots, F_m be a representation of \mathbb{L} . Then we can define a representation of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$ by setting

$$C_i := \{((g, h), (m, n)) \in (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \mid (g, m) \in E_i\} \text{ for } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$$

and

$$D_j := \{((g, h), (m, n)) \in (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \mid (h, n) \in F_j\} \text{ for } j \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

Checking that these together form a representation is then straightforward. \square

In order to find upper bounds on $\text{dim}(\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L})$, we will aspire to merge some of the D_j into the C_i to end up with fewer relations overall. For a Ferrers Relation $F \subseteq G \times M$, we define

$$T(F) := \{(g, m) \in G \times M \setminus F \mid (g_F, m_F) \in F \implies (g, m_F) \in F \text{ or } (g_F, m) \in F\}.$$

If we think of F as a subset of pairs inverted by some linear extension L , then we can also interpret $T(F)$ as the set of pairs (a, b) such that (a, b) does not surround any $(g, m) \in F$ in L . In other words, a configuration like $a \leq m <_L g \leq b$ does not occur in L for any $a, b \in T(F)$. This will become useful as this means we can modify the order of pairs involving a or b with respect to each other in the product, while maintaining the pairs inverted by F . Let us establish some additional structure on $T(F)$.

Lemma 4.4 ([21]). *For a Ferrers Relation $F \subseteq G \times M$, with elements $g_1, g_2 \in G$ and $m_1, m_2 \in M$, $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2), (g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$ implies $(g_2, m_1) \in T(F)$.*

Figure 4.3.: Visually, $T(F)$ outlines the “steps” of a Ferrers Relation F after appropriate reordering of rows and columns. Elements of $T(F)$ are marked with \circ .

Proof. First, observe that $(g_2, m_1) \notin F$, since otherwise $(g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$ would imply $(g_1, m_1) \in F$ or $(g_2, m_2) \in F$, both of which cannot be the case by assumption. Now, let $(\hat{g}, \hat{m}) \in F$ be arbitrary. Then $(g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$ implies that $(g_1, \hat{m}) \in F$ or $(\hat{g}, m_2) \in F$. If $(g_1, \hat{m}) \in F$, then $(g_2, m_2) \in T(F)$ implies $(g_1, m_2) \in F$ or $(g_2, \hat{m}) \in F$. Thus $(g_2, \hat{m}) \in F$, because $(g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$ and thus is not in F . Similarly, if $(\hat{g}, m_2) \in F$, then $(g_1, m_1) \in T(F)$ implies $(g_2, \hat{m}) \in F$.

Now (g_2, m_1) fulfills all of the required conditions and so $(g_2, m_1) \in T(F)$. \square

We can use this to define an equivalence relation on $T(F)$.

Lemma 4.5 ([21]). *Define a relation \sim on $T(F)$ by $(g_1, m_1) \sim (g_2, m_2)$ if and only if $(g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$ and $(g_2, m_1) \in T(F)$. Then \sim is an equivalence relation.*

Proof. The relation is clearly reflexive and symmetric. To prove transitivity, let

$$(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2), (g_3, m_3) \in T(F), (g_1, m_1) \sim (g_2, m_2), (g_2, m_2) \sim (g_3, m_3).$$

Now, by definition $(g_1, m_2), (g_2, m_2), (g_2, m_3) \in T(F)$. Applying Lemma 4.4 then yields $(g_1, m_3) \in T(F)$ as well as $(g_3, m_1) \in T(F)$. \square

Lemma 4.6 ([21]). *For a Ferrers Relation $F \subseteq G \times M$, if $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2) \in T(F)$ and $(g_1, m_1) \approx (g_2, m_2)$, then $(g_1, m_2) \in F$ or $(g_2, m_1) \in F$.*

Proof. If $(g_1, m_2) \in T(F)$, then $(g_1, m_1) \sim (g_2, m_2)$ by Lemma 4.4. So suppose $(g_1, m_2) \notin T(F)$ and $(g_1, m_2) \notin F$. Then there exists $(\hat{g}, \hat{m}) \in F$, such that $(g_1, \hat{m}) \notin F$ and $(\hat{g}, m_2) \notin F$. Now $(g_1, m_1) \in T(F)$ and $(\hat{g}, \hat{m}) \in F$ implies $(\hat{g}, m_1) \in F$. Combining this with $(g_2, m_2) \in T(F)$ yields that $(g_2, m_1) \in F$. \square

With these preliminaries established, we can finally formulate the theorem. We say that a context \mathbb{K} has the (r, s) -covering property if there is a representation F_1, \dots, F_s of \mathbb{K} , where for each $i \in \{1, \dots, s\}$ there exists a partition $T_{i,1}, \dots, T_{i,r}$ of $T(F_i)$ in \sim -closed classes, such that $I \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^s T_{i,j}$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, r\}$.

Theorem 4.7. *Let $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I_{\mathbb{K}})$ and $\mathbb{L} = (H, N, I_{\mathbb{L}})$ be contexts. If \mathbb{K} has the (r, s) -covering property, then*

$$\text{fdim}(\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}) \leq s + \text{fdim}(\mathbb{L}) - \min(r, \text{fdim}(\mathbb{L})).$$

Proof. Let $t = \min(r, \text{fdim}(\mathbb{L}))$. Because \mathbb{K} has the (r, s) -covering property there exists a representation E_1, \dots, E_k and partitions of $T(E_i)$ into \sim -closed classes $T_{i,j}, \dots, T_{i,r}$. Also, let F_1, \dots, F_l be a representation of \mathbb{L} . Define

$$C_i := \{((g, h), (m, n)) \in (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \mid (g, m) \in E_i \\ \text{or there exists } j \in \{1, \dots, t\} \text{ with } (g, m) \in T_{i,j} \text{ and } (h, n) \in F_j\} \text{ for } i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$$

and

$$D_j := \{((g, h), (m, n)) \in (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \mid (h, n) \in F_j\} \text{ for } j \in \{t+1, \dots, l\}.$$

We claim that the C_i and D_j form a representation of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$. First, let us check that each pair in $S := (G \times H) \times (M \times N) \setminus I$ is covered. Let $p := ((g, h), (m, n)) \in S$. If $(g, m) \in G \times M \setminus I_{\mathbb{K}}$, then (g, m) is covered by one of the E_i and therefore p is covered by C_i . Otherwise suppose $(g, h) \in I_{\mathbb{K}}$ and $(h, n) \in H \times N \setminus I_{\mathbb{L}}$. Then (h, n) is covered by one of the F_j . If $j > t$, then p is covered by D_j . Otherwise there is i such that $(g, m) \in T_{i,j}$ and by definition p is then covered by C_i .

It remains to be shown that each of the constructed relations is a Ferrers Relation. This is clear for the D_j . For the C_i , let $((g_1, h_1), (m_1, n_1)), ((g_2, h_2), (m_2, n_2)) \in C_i$. If $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2) \in E_i$, then $(g_1, m_2) \in E_i$ or $(g_2, m_1) \in E_i$. Thus $((g_1, h_1), (m_2, n_2)) \in C_i$ or $((g_2, h_2), (m_1, n_1)) \in C_i$ by definition of C_i . If $(g_1, m_1) \in E_i$ and $(g_2, m_2) \in T(E_i)$, then the definition of $T(E_i)$ implies that $(g_1, m_2) \in E_i$ or $(g_2, m_1) \in E_i$. Lastly suppose $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2) \in T(E_i)$. If $(g_1, m_1) \approx (g_2, m_2)$, then by Lemma 4.6 $(g_1, m_2) \in E_i$ or $(g_2, m_1) \in E_i$. Now if $(g_1, m_1) \sim (g_2, m_2)$, recall that the $T_{i,j}$ form a partition of $T(E_i)$ into closed classes. So, $(g_1, m_1), (g_2, m_2), (g_1, m_2), (g_2, m_1)$ are contained within the same $T_{i,j}$. This means that $(h_1, n_1), (h_2, n_2)$ are both contained in F_j . Hence, (h_1, n_2) or (h_2, n_1) is in F_j and thus $((g_1, h_1), (m_2, n_2)) \in C_i$ or $((g_2, h_2), (m_1, n_1)) \in C_i$ again by definition of C_i . \square

4.2.2. Reformulating the Covering Property

At a first glance, it is not immediately obvious how to translate these ideas to linear extensions directly, but it turns out that the core ideas behind the covering property exactly correspond to those used in Proposition 3.1 and Theorem 3.11. It is best to work through a few examples to get a more concrete picture. Recall the Fence poset from Section 3.1. Its unique realizer is given by

$$L_1 = a_0 a_1 b_1 a_2 b_2 \dots a_n b_n \\ L_2 = a_n a_{n-1} b_n a_{n-2} b_{n-1} \dots a_0 b_1.$$

In Proposition 3.1, to find a realizer of $F_n \times Q$, we grouped the ascending pairs together and applied a linear extension of a minimal realizer of Q to each of these groups. If we just mark these groups within L_1 and L_2 with parentheses we get

$$L_1 = (a_0)(a_1 b_1)(a_2 b_2) \dots (a_n b_n) \\ L_2 = (a_n)(a_{n-1} b_n)(a_{n-2} b_{n-1}) \dots (a_0 b_1),$$

where the key property of those groups was that for each pair (a, b) with $a \leq b$ they are contained in some group of L_1 or L_2 and for each pair (x, y) with $x \not\leq y$ there is some i such that $y <_{L_i} x$ and x, y are not both contained in any group of L_i . In general we can attempt to find such realizers and groupings for arbitrary posets P , and if the desired properties hold, the proof of the proposition goes through without difficulty. These assumptions allow us to merge one of the linear extensions of Q with a realizer of P in a linear extension of $P \times Q$ to end up with a realizer of size $\dim(P) + \dim(Q) - 1$.

Building on this, recall that in Theorem 3.11 we managed to merge two linear extensions of Q with a realizer of C_d . Recall that the realizer with its groups highlighted is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= (a_1 a_k b_1)(a_2 \dots a_{k-1} b_2 \dots b_k), \\ L_2 &= (a_1 a_2 b_2)(a_3 b_3) \dots (a_{k-1} b_{k-1})(a_k b_k b_1), \\ L_3 &= (a_k a_{k-1} b_k)(a_{k-2} b_{k-1}) \dots (a_2 b_3)(a_1 b_2 b_1). \end{aligned}$$

In the proof, we do not always apply the same linear extension to a group, but one of two extensions. We therefore distinguish the groups by colors, depending on which linear extension was applied. Again, each pair with (x, y) with $x \not\leq_{C_n} y$ is inverted outside of one group and each pair with $x \leq y$ is contained within a group. More precisely, every such pair is actually contained within two different groups and we can partition the groups into two classes (highlighted by the colors) such that each comparable pair is contained within a group of each color class. This now allows us to merge two extensions of Q into the L_i by applying different extensions to each class of groups. And again, if we find such groupings and extensions for arbitrary poset P , we can use that to determine a realizer of size $\dim(P) + \dim(Q) - 2$.

All of these constructs can also be found in the proof of Theorem 4.7. For a fixed linear extension L with its groups specified, let F_L be the set of pairs (a, b) where $b <_L a$ and a, b are not contained in the same group. F_L is a Ferrers Relation, as we can order elements by their groups to get a staircase shape. $T(F_L)$ then consists of those pairs, that do not surround any of the pairs in F . Equivalently, this is the set of all pairs a, b such that both are contained in some group of L . Finally, each \sim -closed class directly corresponds to one of the groups and the coloring yields the partition $T_{i,1}, \dots, T_{i,k}$.

With all of these considerations, it is possible to formulate Theorem 4.7 directly on partial orders instead of Ferrers Relations. For any linear extension L we define a *block* to be a contiguous subsequence of L . Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a poset and $R = L_1, \dots, L_s$ be a realizer of P . Then R has the r -covering property if for each $i \in \{1, \dots, s\}$ there exist disjoint blocks of L_i partitioned into r color classes $T_{i,1}, \dots, T_{i,r}$, such that for each $j \in \{1, \dots, r\}$ and $x, y \in X$ with $x \leq y$, there is an i such that x and y are contained within one block of $T_{i,j}$ and for each pair x, y with $x \not\leq y$, there is i such that $y <_{L_i} x$ and there is no block of $\bigcup_{j=1}^r T_{i,j}$ containing both x and y . We say that a poset P has the (r, s) -covering property if it has a realizer of size s with the r -covering property.

Theorem 4.8. *Let P, Q be posets. If P has the (r, s) -covering property, then*

$$\dim(P \times Q) \leq s + \dim(Q) - \min(r, \dim(Q)).$$

For partial orders, this formulation is fully equivalent to the definition given by Reuter. Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a poset and $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, I)$ be its corresponding context. We will construct a (r, s) -covering realizer of P from an (r, s) -covering representation of \mathbb{K} .

Let $F \subseteq X \times X \setminus I$ be a Ferrers relation. For a \sim -closed class C of $T(F)$, define $B(C) = \{a \in X \mid \exists x : (a, x) \in C \cap I \text{ or } (x, a) \in C \cap I\}$. These sets $B(C)$ will represent the blocks of the r, s -covering of P . First we need to establish that each element is contained only within exactly one block.

Lemma 4.9. *Let $a \in X$, then a is contained in at most one set $B(C)$.*

Proof. Suppose there are \sim -closed classes C_1, C_2 such that $a \in B(C_1)$ and $a \in B(C_2)$. Therefore, there exist x_1, x_2 such that (x_1, a) or (a, x_1) in $C_1 \cap I$ and (x_2, a) or (a, x_2) in $C_2 \cap I$. If $(x_1, a) \in C_1 \cap I$ and $(x_2, a) \in C_2 \cap I$, then by Lemma 4.6 $(x_1, a) \in F$ or $(x_2, a) \in F$, contradicting our initial assumptions. If $(x_1, a) \in C_1 \cap I$ and $(a, x_2) \in C_2 \cap I$, then by Lemma 4.6 either (a, a) or (x_1, x_2) is in F . But $(a, a) \in I$ by reflexivity of I and $(x_1, x_2) \in I$ by transitivity. So this also cannot be. \square

Next we show that we can order these blocks well within any linear extension covering all pairs of F .

Lemma 4.10. *Let C_1, C_2 be \sim -closed classes of F . Then in any linear extension covering all pairs of F either $a_1 < a_2$ for all $a_1 \in B(C_1), a_2 \in B(C_2)$ or $a_2 < a_1$ for all $a_1 \in B(C_1), a_2 \in B(C_2)$.*

Proof. There exist x_1, x_2 such that (x_1, a) or (a, x_1) in $C_1 \cap I$ and (x_2, a) or (a, x_2) in $C_2 \cap I$. If $(x_1, a) \in C_1 \cap I$ and $(x_2, b) \in C_2 \cap I$ then again by Lemma 4.6 either (x_1, b) or (x_2, a) in F . If now $(x_1, b) \in F$, then it must be that $x_2 \leq b < x_1 \leq a$ in any linear extension of F . By exchanging x_1 and a as well as x_2 and b , we get the same result for all other cases. We still need to show that we get the same ordering independent of the choice of representative of $B(C_1)$ and $B(C_2)$. So let $(x_1, a) \in C_1, (x_2, b) \in C_2$ and $(x_1, b) \in F$. Now, suppose there is a different pair $(\bar{x}_1, \bar{a}) \in C_1 \cap I$ such that $(x_2, \bar{a}) \in F$. By definition of a Ferrers Relation and $(x_1, b), (x_2, \bar{a}) \in F$ we must have $(x_1, \bar{a}) \in F$ or $(x_2, b) \in F$. But $(x_2, b) \in C_2$ and therefore is not in F and as $(x_1, a), (\bar{x}_1, \bar{a}) \in C_1$, they are equivalent under \sim so $(x_1, \bar{a}) \in C_1$ and thus not in F . \square

This means that F induces a well-defined ordering of the blocks in each linear extension F in such a way that they do not interfere with each other. Last but not least, we need to show that forming blocks around each of the $B(C)$ maintains that no pairs in F end up in the same block.

Lemma 4.11. *Let $(g, m) \in F$. Let L be any linear extension L covering all pairs of F . After forming minimal blocks in L around $B(C)$ for all \sim -closed classes C , g and m are not contained in the same block.*

Proof. For some \sim -closed C , the set $B(C)$ has some minimal element a and maximal element b in L . By definition of $B(C)$, there are $x, y \in X$ with $(a, y) \in C \cap I$ and $(x, b) \in C \cap I$ and thus by definition of \sim , we get $(a, b) \in C$. Now, for any $(g, m) \in F$ we get that $(a, m) \in F$ or $(g, b) \in F$ as $(a, b) \in T(F)$. Thus $m <_L a$ or $b <_L g$, but because a or b was the minimum or maximum respectively of $B(C)$ in L one of m or g is thus not contained in the block $B(C)$. \square

This means that for $P = (X, \leq)$ and $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, \leq)$, we can construct a (r, s) -covering realizer from any (r, s) -covering representation by applying the operation as described above. For each F in the representation, take any linear extension covering all pairs of F and then form blocks around the $B(C)$ and color them according to the color prescribed by the $T_{i,j}$. To get from a (r, s) -covering realizer to a (r, s) -covering representation we define F as the set of pairs (g, m) such that $m < g$ and g, m are not contained in any block. Showing that \sim -closed classes of $T(F)$ correspond exactly to the blocks is then not difficult.

Theorem 4.12. *Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a poset and $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, \leq)$ be its corresponding context. P is (r, s) -covering if and only if \mathbb{K} is (r, s) -covering.*

4.2.3. Examples of Coverings

Fact 4.3 can also be described by the covering property. Clearly every poset P is $(0, \dim(P))$ -covering. Similarly, any poset P is $(k, \dim(P) + k)$ covering for all $k \geq 0$. This can be shown by starting with any realizer of P and then adding additional extensions, where all elements are contained in a single block.

To find meaningful examples with interesting upper bounds, we are generally looking for (r, s) -covering realizers of P maximizing $r - s$. If we can find a (r, s) -covering realizer for some P with $r - s \geq 3$ this would disprove Conjecture 1.6. Because of this, we are usually trying to find realizers with s minimal, that is $s = \dim(P)$. Thus we will say that a poset P has the r -covering property, if it has the $(r, \dim(P))$ -covering property. It is in theory possible to gain an additional larger increase in r by increasing s , but no examples, where this produces any such benefit, are known.

We have already discussed two concrete examples for the covering property. Fences are 1-covering and the k -crowns for $k \geq 3$ are 2-covering. In general Reuter noted that there are many 1-covering posets, yet he only knew of few 2-covering posets. This can also be verified by looking at Appendix A, according to which crowns are the only 2-covering 3-irreducible posets.

Other examples of 2-covering posets he mentioned were antichains and Standard Examples, although he did not prove any of these properties. Finding the 2-covering of the Standard Example S_n is luckily not difficult. See Appendix B for a list of examples of posets and their coverings.

Note that any poset with $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$ does not have the k -covering property for any $k \geq 1$, because the pair $(\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{0})$ cannot be covered by $T(F)$ if F is non-empty. This is also a

consequence of Theorem 1.8. Something that may seem surprising, is that only the covering property of one of the posets influences the upper bound, regardless of one or both posets have the covering property. But this is consistent with the known result about $\dim(S_n \times S_m)$ by Trotter [27] and Lin [20] and also generally agrees with the results we have calculated in Chapter 2.

Reuter also mentioned that under certain conditions, which he did not describe in detail, the 2-covering property is maintained under the bipyramid construction we discussed in Section 3.1. We give a formal proof here, using our definition of 2-covering.

Proposition 4.13. *Let P be a poset and $R = L_1, \dots, L_k$ be a 2-covering realizer of P with the property that for each i , the first block of L_i always has color two and all other blocks have color 1. Then the two-covering property holds under the bipyramid construction. That is, $B(P)$ is $(2, k + 1)$ -covering.*

Proof. Recall that $B(P)$ contains three copies of P . For $x \in P$ we denote the same element in the lower copy P_0 by x^0 and analogously define x^1 and x^2 for the upper copies. For an element x in 1 of the copies, we denote its original in P by $\pi(x)$. Suppose L_i and its 2-covering coloring is given by

$$(x_1, \dots, x_n)(y_{1,1}, \dots, y_{1,t_1})(y_{2,1}, \dots, y_{2,t_2}) \dots (y_{s,t_s}, \dots, y_{s,t_s}),$$

where the first block is marked with color 2, and all other blocks are colored with color 1. Then we define a corresponding linear extension L'_i of $B(P)$ with its block coloring by

$$\begin{aligned} & (l_2, x_1^0, x_1^2, x_2^0, x_2^2, \dots, x_n^0, x_n^2) \\ & (l_1, x_1^1, x_2^1, \dots, x_n^1) \\ & (y_{1,1}^0, y_{1,1}^1, y_{1,1}^2, y_{1,2}^0, y_{1,2}^1, y_{1,2}^2, \dots, y_{1,t_1}^0, y_{1,t_1}^1, y_{1,t_1}^2) \\ & (y_{2,1}^0, y_{2,1}^1, y_{2,1}^2, y_{2,2}^0, y_{2,2}^1, y_{2,2}^2, \dots, y_{2,t_2}^0, y_{2,t_2}^1, y_{2,t_2}^2) \\ & \quad \vdots \\ & (y_{s,1}^0, y_{s,1}^1, y_{s,1}^2, y_{s,2}^0, y_{s,2}^1, y_{s,2}^2, \dots, y_{s,t_s}^0, y_{s,t_s}^1, y_{s,t_s}^2). \end{aligned}$$

Also define one last extension L'_{k+1} by

$$(l_1, p_1^0, p_1^1, \dots, p_n^0, p_n^1)(l_2, p_1^2, \dots, p_n^2),$$

where p_1, \dots, p_n is an arbitrary linear extension of P . We claim that these are linear extensions and that they form a 2-covering realizer.

First convince yourself that these are indeed linear extensions. This can be seen by acknowledging that we mostly follow the order given by L_i . To see that they form a 2-covering realizer, we need to check that for all elements a, b of $B(P)$ with $a \not\leq b$, there is an extension L'_i such that $b <_{L'_i} a$ and a, b are not contained in the same block.

In the following, bear in mind that each element x of P appears in the first block of L_i for some i , since the first block is the only one with color 2. There are a few cases which we need to consider. If elements x, y of P are in different blocks of L_i , then regardless

which copy of x or y in $B(P)$ is taken, they are still in different blocks in L'_i . Therefore we just need to prove the remaining cases where $a \not\leq b$ in P but $\pi(a) \leq \pi(b)$. This occurs in one of two possible cases. If $a \in P_1$ and $b \in P_2$ or $b \in P_0$, then by construction there is L_i such that $\pi(b)$ is in the first block of L_i and thus b is in the first block of L'_i , which does not contain a . If $a \in P_2$ and $b \in P_1$ or $b \in P_0$ then the property is fulfilled in L'_{k+1} .

We also need to check that each pair $a, b \in B(P)$ with $a \leq b$ is covered by one block of each color. If $\pi(a), \pi(b)$ is covered by a block of color 1 by one of the L_i , then it is also covered by a block of color 1 in L'_i . If $a = l_1$, then $b \in P_1$ and there is L_i such that b is contained in the first block and thus (l_1, b) is contained in the second block of L'_i .

Otherwise if $a = l_2$, then $b \in P_2$ and the block is covered by color 1 in L'_{k+1} . For color 2, all pairs involving elements of P_1 are covered in the first block of L_{k+1} . For all other pairs, the corresponding pair $\pi(a), \pi(b)$ is covered by the first block of some L_i and thus also by the first block of L'_i . \square

Most of the 2-covering posets we discussed here fulfill the requirements for this proposition. One can find such realizers for the antichain A_2 , any d -Crown with $d \geq 3$ and any Standard Example S_n . It does not apply to any antichain A_k with $k \geq 3$, as the ‘‘center’’ elements are never contained within the first block of a 2-covering realizer, and indeed one can check that the resulting poset $B(A_k)$ has dimension 3 but is not 2-covering.

Take note that the result of the construction maintains the properties needed to apply it, so we can iterate the construction repeatedly. Using this in conjunction with polytope duality now implies that the face lattices of cubes without $\mathbf{0}$ or $\mathbf{1}$ are 2-covering. Indeed the realizer for the 4-crown – which is the face lattice of a 2-cube – we defined in Theorem 3.11 can be constructed by applying Proposition 4.13 to A_2 .

For essentially all of the products of P, Q we discussed up to this point, the dimension of $P \times Q$ corresponds to the bound given by the covering property. This is not entirely true in general. As an example observe the poset P in Figure 4.4. This is a 3-dimensional poset that contains the Boolean Lattice B_2 , thus $\dim(P \times P) \geq 4$ and one can calculate that equality holds. But P is not 2-covering as $\dim(P \times B_2) = 4 > \dim(P) + 2 - 2$. That said, the ideas behind the covering property still provide a suitable explanation. Consider the disjoint union of the Boolean Lattice B_2 and the 3-Crown C_3 . Let $\hat{P} := B_2 + C_3$. Then \hat{P} is a 3-dimensional poset that is not 2-covering as $\hat{P} \times B_2$ contains B_4 and thus has dimension 4. But $\dim(\hat{P} \times \hat{P}) \cong C_3^2 + 2 \cdot B_2 \times C_3 + B_2^2$, the connected components of which all have dimension bounded by four by the covering property. Hence $\dim(\hat{P} \times \hat{P}) = 4$. Now P is just C_3 with has a copy of B_2 inserted into one edge and in this case it behaves similarly to the disjoint union, when it comes to dimension.

Figure 4.4.: Connected poset P with $\dim(P) = 3$, $\dim(P^2) = 4$ and $\dim(P \times B_2) = 4$.

5. Outlook

In this chapter we would like to present further problems that may be of interest, and the difficulties we encountered attempting to solve them. We will also provide a brief recap of our results.

5.1. Further Research

5.1.1. Characterizing the Covering Property

Reuter [21, p. 290] also described a conjecture that every product of contexts \mathbb{K}, \mathbb{L} admits a realizer that in a sense looks like the ones we described in the previous section. For contexts $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I_{\mathbb{K}})$ and $\mathbb{L} = (H, N, I_{\mathbb{L}})$, let X_1, \dots, X_k be a representation of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$. Define

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{\mathbb{K}}(X_i) &:= \{(g, m) \in G \times M \setminus I_{\mathbb{K}} \mid \exists (h, n) \in H \times N : ((g, h), (m, n)) \in X_i\}, \\ \pi_{\mathbb{L}}(X_i) &:= \{(h, n) \in H \times N \setminus I_{\mathbb{L}} \mid \exists (g, m) \in G \times M : ((g, h), (m, n)) \in X_i\}.\end{aligned}$$

Now call a representation X_1, \dots, X_k of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$ *canonical* if all $\pi_{\mathbb{K}}(X_i)$ or all $\pi_{\mathbb{L}}(X_i)$ are Ferrers Relations.

Conjecture 5.1 ([21]). *One can always find a canonical representation X_1, \dots, X_k of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$ with $k = \text{fdim}(\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L})$.*

To be perfectly honest, we are not entirely sure what exactly this conjecture is supposed to represent, as Reuter was frustratingly brief in his description. The condition that *all* $\pi_{\mathbb{K}}(X_i)$ or *all* $\pi_{\mathbb{L}}(X_i)$ are Ferrers Relation is not fulfilled for the construction from Fact 4.3, as $\pi_{\mathbb{L}}(C_i) = H \times N \setminus I_{\mathbb{L}}$ and $\pi_{\mathbb{K}}(D_i) = G \times M \setminus I_{\mathbb{K}}$. Initially we thought that posets P, Q both of which have $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$, would offer a clear counterexample to the conjecture but this did not turn out to be true, at least for small examples such as $B_2 \times B_2$. The idea was that any realizer of $P \times Q$ must have linear extensions L_1 and L_2 with $(\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q) <_{L_1} (\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q)$ and $(\mathbf{1}_P, \mathbf{0}_Q) <_{L_2} (\mathbf{0}_P, \mathbf{1}_Q)$. Thus we would get

$$\begin{aligned}(\mathbf{0}_P, q_2) &<_{L_1} (\mathbf{1}_P, q_1) \text{ for all } q_1, q_2 \in Q, \\ (p_2, \mathbf{0}_Q) &<_{L_2} (p_1, \mathbf{1}_Q) \text{ for all } p_1, p_2 \in P.\end{aligned}$$

If we now view the corresponding contexts $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, \leq_P)$ and $\mathbb{L} = (Y, Y, \leq_Q)$ then $\pi_{\mathbb{L}}(L_1) = H \times N \setminus I_{\mathbb{L}}$ and $\pi_{\mathbb{K}}(L_2) = G \times M \setminus I$. Both of these would not be Ferrers Relations unless P and Q have dimension 1. But this argument fails when considering

a representation of $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{L}$, as the additional degrees of freedom afforded by not being forced to choose one orientation for each incomparable pair still allow one to choose a canonical covering.

Similarly, it would be nice to find additional characterizations on the covering property to get definite results on its importance. For instance, let P be a poset and Q be a poset with $\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}$. Is it then true that $\dim(P \times Q) = \dim(P) + \dim(Q) - r$ if and only if P is r -covering? We worked on this problem a little bit, but the difficulty we encountered was that arbitrary realizers of $P \times Q$ just do not have enough structure to allow one to easily construct a r -covering realizer of P . Finding a canonical covering may thus fix this issue.

Further research of the covering property and its importance seems warranted. We will refrain from formulating a concrete conjecture about canonical coverings for posets $P \times Q$, as cases like the example in Figure 4.4 may make these awkward to formulate. We still believe that it is likely that, for many cases like irreducible posets, the dimension of the product is completely determined by the covering property.

5.1.2. Powers of Posets

When Felsner showed us how to determine the dimension of cube-grids, one of the first generalizations we considered was studying the dimension of powers of posets, because the original proof in essence determines the dimension of $F_k^n = \underbrace{F_k \times \cdots \times F_k}_{n\text{-times}}$. Define

such powers by setting $P^1 = P$ and $P^n = P \times P^{n-1}$ for $n > 1$. The questions for the order dimension of cartesian product can then also be asked for this exponentiation. In particular the sequences $\dim(P^n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ may be of interest. As of now, there are no meaningful publications tackling this problem. Of course, this is likely to be quite challenging, considering the difficulties we faced producing results for just the product. We did not manage to produce very meaningful results on this topic. Regardless, we will discuss some preliminary definitions and results.

Let $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 1$, then for the following posets the dimension of P^n is already known. If A is an antichain, then $\dim(A^n) = 2$ as A^n has no comparable pairs. For any chain C , Theorem 1.8 implies that $\dim(C^n) = n$. Indeed we can apply Theorem 1.8 for any poset P with $\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}$ and $\dim(P) = d$ to get $\dim(P^n) = d \cdot n$. In Subsection 3.1.1, we determine the dimension of F^n for non-trivial Fences as $\dim(F^n) = n + 1$. Proving a lower bound for products with $C_k, k \geq 3$ would imply that $\dim(C_k^n) = n + 2$, but this remains unproven.

A good initial question to ask with regards to this is whether increasing the exponent always increases the dimension by the same amount. In essence, we ask whether $\dim(P^{n+1}) - \dim(P^n)$ is some constant only depending on P . On first glance, this happens to be true for all the posets we discussed above, but this does not hold in general. The counter-examples here are the same as the ones we discussed at the end of Subsection 4.2.3. Declare P to be the disjoint union of the 3-Crown C_3 and the Boolean Lattice B_2 . Then $\dim(P) = 3$ as $\max(\dim(C_3), \dim(B_2)) = 2$. As already mentioned

$\dim(P \times P) = 4$ and because P contains B_2 , P^3 contains B_6 and thus $\dim(P^3) \geq 6$. But this now implies $\dim(P^2) - \dim(P) = 1 \neq 2 \leq \dim(P^3) - \dim(P^2)$. A connected counterexample is again given by the poset in Figure 4.4.

That said, it is not hard to prove that for the disconnected example $\dim(P^n) = 2n$ for $n \geq 4$. So it may be true that the sequence $\dim(P^{n+1}) - \dim(P^n)$ always eventually stabilizes when n is large enough.

To get started one can define the *power dimension* by

$$\text{pdim}(P) := \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \dim(P^{n+1}) - \dim(P^n),$$

which always exists, as $0 \leq \dim(P^{n+1}) - \dim(P^n) \leq \dim(P)$. If P contains any comparable pair we then get for example $1 \leq \text{pdim}(P)$, because B^n is contained in P^n , so the sequence $\dim(P^n)$ is unbounded. Known values for power dimension thus are $\text{pdim}(A_k) = 0$, $\text{pdim}(F_k) = 1$ and $\text{pdim}(C_k) = 1$. In addition $\text{pdim}(P) = \dim(P)$ for all P with $\mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{1}$. This now begs a clear question.

Question 5.2. *Is $\text{pdim}(P \times Q) = \text{pdim}(P) + \text{pdim}(Q)$?*

This is true for at least one non-trivial example. Let $P := B_k \times F_l$ for some $k, l \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$\dim(P^n) = \dim(B_k \times F_l^n) = \dim(B_k^n \times F_l^n) = nk + n$$

and thus

$$\dim(P^{n+1}) - \dim(P^n) = ((n+1)k + n + 1) - (nk + n) = k + 1.$$

$\dim(B_k^n \times F_l^n) = nk + n$ follows from Theorem 3.2 and Proposition 3.1. One could also consider alternative definitions for power dimension, such as replacing \limsup by \liminf or setting the power dimension to $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\dim(P^n)}{n}$. Note that in the last case, one can show that the limit always exists using $\dim(P+Q) \leq \dim(P) + \dim(Q)$ but it is unclear whether this is always integral.

While we think that this topic deserves more research, meaningful insights likely require deeper insights about the order dimension of products, which have yet to be found.

5.1.3. Miscellaneous

Lower bounds for crowns. A clear goal would be to prove a corresponding lower bound for Theorem 3.11. We believe, that $\dim(P \times C_k) \geq \dim(P) + 1$ for any P and any k -Crown with $k \geq 3$. Results such as Theorem 3.2 indicate that this is probably true. Moreover, we know that $\dim(P \times V) \geq \dim(P) + 1$ if P has a $\mathbf{0}$ and $\dim(P \times F_2) \geq \dim(P) + 1$ if P has a $\mathbf{1}$. A larger Fence now already contains V and F_2 as subposets. Now, crowns not only contain large fences but in addition to that crowns have their cyclic structure. So this result would not be surprising. In our calculations, this also seemed to hold for all posets for which we calculated the dimension of the product with C_k , yet

ultimately we were unable to find a proof, even though we spent a significant amount of time on this problem. In a sense, this theorem might be deeper than apparent at first glance. For instance, because $\dim(C_k) = 3$ the lower bound would imply that $\dim(C_k \times P) \geq \dim(P) + \dim(C_k) - 2$ for all P , so P could not be 3-covering. But proving that 3-covering posets do not exist may be quite difficult. Lastly, since crowns are also the only 2-covering 3-irreducible posets, this indicates that crowns could represent a meaningful barrier with regards to Conjecture 1.6.

Products of 3-dimensional posets. Proving the lower bound for crowns would also complete the proof that $\dim(P \times Q) \geq 4$ for P, Q with $\dim(P) \geq 3$ and $\dim(Q) \geq 3$. This is because, as we already have mentioned in Section 3.2, all 3-irreducible posets that are not a crown or a chevron contain a copy of Z_3 or a “flipped” Z_3 , denoted by \widehat{Z}_3 , and the chevron contains a C_2 . Then in addition to already having determined $\dim(Z_3 \times Z_3) = 4$, one can then also calculate $\dim(Z_3 \times \widehat{Z}_3) = \dim(Z_3 \times C_2) = 4$. So all that remains to be done is to show that $\dim(C_k \times P) \geq 4$ for any 3-irreducible P . Now as some classes of 3-irreducible posets, such as the crowns, consist of infinite families it is not enough to simply check these cases with a computer. We would at least require results that indicate that the behavior with regards to the cartesian product is similar for all posets contained in such a class. Proving this alone appears to be rather tedious as there are seven such infinite families. Besides, it is not obvious what we would gain by completing the proof in such a way. It is true that this would finally disprove Conjecture 1.5, but it is unlikely that this proof would provide useful methods for analyzing the dimension of products in general.

k -dimension. Somewhat recently, there has been an effort by Baym and West [2] to determine the k -dimension of products of orders. To give a brief introduction, a classic result by Hiraguchi [16] states that $\dim(P)$ is equal to the smallest t such that P can be embedded into the product of t chains. These chains may be arbitrarily long, but if we bound the size of these chains, we get the k -dimension. So the k -dimension of a partial order P is equal to the smallest t such that P can be embedded into the t -times product of the k -chain. That said, it is not obvious whether any of our methods translate well to k -dimension as it does behave quite differently. For instance, the k -dimension of antichains is unbounded because the t -times product of k -chains is a finite poset and thus has bounded width.

Other grids. Niklas Affolter advised us that it may be interesting to consider grids other than cube grids. A special example of these would be root lattices, although they are only tangentially related to our research. The cube grid for instance arises from the type A root lattice. The first step in all of this would likely be to work out the dimensions of the contained polytopes. This is already known for dimension 3 [7], but requires further research in higher dimensions.

5.2. Conclusion

The methods we described to calculate order dimension in Chapter 2 ended up being quite promising, producing good results with comparatively little effort. Making these results available through SageMath would make this easily accessible and allow for anyone to engage with poset dimension more easily, so we hope to accomplish this soon.

We also managed to complete our initial goals for this thesis, which was to complete the proof of the dimension of the grid and proving the characterization of fences. Rediscovering the covering property along the way was a little sobering in the sense that Reuter would have likely had little difficulty providing similar proofs, but we were quite close to discovering the property independently. Finally, we think that recontextualizing coverings as well as filling the gaps in Reuters papers does make for meaningful results.

As a final takeaway we encourage the reader to pay attention to the covering property, if they were to encounter products of posets in the wild. While theoretical results on the lower bound are still outstanding, it really appears that, in practice, analyzing the covering property is what is needed to determine dimension.

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Appendix A.

Dimension of Products of 3-irreducible Posets

We give the dimension of products of 3-irreducible posets, calculated by the methods mentioned in Chapter 2 here. The posets are labeled the same as in the original source by Kelly [17]. Of course, there are infinitely many 3-irreducible posets, so not every poset is represented in this table. But as 3-irreducible posets decompose into a number of similar families, we have taken the smallest representative of each of these families and calculated the dimensions of their products.

	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>CX</i> ₁	<i>CX</i> ₂	<i>CX</i> ₃	<i>D</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>EX</i> ₁	<i>EX</i> ₂	<i>FX</i> ₁	<i>FX</i> ₂	<i>H</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>J</i>
<i>A</i>	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
<i>B</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>C</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>CX</i> ₁	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>CX</i> ₂	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>CX</i> ₃	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>D</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>E</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>EX</i> ₁	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>EX</i> ₂	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>FX</i> ₁	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>FX</i> ₂	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>H</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>I</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
<i>F</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6
<i>G</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6
<i>J</i>	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	6

Table A.1.: The Dimension of Products of 3-irreducible posets.

Appendix B.

Examples of Coverings

Let us give a few important examples for the covering property here. Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a poset and $\mathbb{K} = (X, X, I)$ be its corresponding context. In the original paper by Reuter [21], coverings are usually given by $r + 1$ tables, if \mathbb{K} is (r, s) -covering. The first table describes the context \mathbb{K} and its representation. For $1 \leq j \leq r$ the $j + 1$ -th table contains the $\bigcup_{i=1}^s T_{i,j}$, marked by number i if $(g, m) \in T_{i,j}$. The advantages of this are that this usually a compact representation of the covering as r is small and it is easy to check whether $I \supseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^s T_{i,j}$ for each j . The disadvantage is, that the $T(F_i)$ are not visible in this drawing and we also have to present incomplete information in case anything is covered twice.

Alternatively one may want to visualize each F_i together with $T(F_i)$ in its own table, which takes up significantly more space for large s but is more easy to interpret in our opinion. In this case we mark $(g, m) \in T(F)$ with \circ and the $T_{i,j}$ with colors. Of course we can also give a covering realizer in the style of Theorem 4.8 to describe coverings.

The given examples should be interpreted as follows. In the first row, we give the poset and its corresponding (reduced) context. In the second row, we draw the representation of the covering as given by Reuter. In the third row we draw a table for each F_i and we finish with the two-covering realizer of each poset.

In all of the given examples it should not be challenging to extrapolate the general case from the specific example we have given.

Figure B.1.: 2-covering of the antichain A_5

×	×	1	1	1	1	1
2	×	×	1	1	1	1
2	2	×	×	1	1	1
2	2	2	×	×	1	1
2	2	2	2	×	×	1
2	2	2	2	2	×	×

2	1					
	2	1				
		2	1			
			2	1		
				2	1	
					2	1

⊗	⊗	1	1	1	1	1
	×	⊗	1	1	1	1
		×	⊗	1	1	1
			×	⊗	1	1
				×	⊗	1
					×	⊗

⊗	×					
2	⊗	×				
2	2	⊗	×			
2	2	2	⊗	×		
2	2	2	2	⊗	×	
2	2	2	2	2	⊗	⊗

$$(a_5)(a_4b_5)(a_3b_4)(a_2b_3)(a_1b_2)(a_0b_1)$$

$$(a_0)(a_1b_1)(a_2b_2)(a_3b_3)(a_4b_4)(a_5b_5)$$

Figure B.2.: 1-covering of the fence F_6

$$\begin{aligned}
& (a_5 a_4 b_5)(a_3 b_4)(a_2 b_3)(a_1 b_1 b_2) \\
& (a_5 a_1 b_1)(a_2 b_2)(a_3 b_3)(a_4 b_4 b_5) \\
& (a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 b_2 b_3 b_4)(a_5 b_5 b_1)
\end{aligned}$$

Figure B.3.: 2-covering of the 5-crown C_5

	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5
a_1		×	×	×	×
a_2	×		×	×	×
a_3	×	×		×	×
a_4	×	×	×		×
a_5	×	×	×	×	

1	×	×	×	×
×	2	×	×	×
×	×	3	×	×
×	×	×	4	×
×	×	×	×	5

	1	1	1	1
2		2	2	2
3	3		3	3
4	4	4		4
5	5	5	5	

		2	3	4	5
1			3	4	5
1	2			4	5
1	2	3			5
1	2	3	4		

1	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
⊗		×	×	×
⊗	×		×	×
⊗	×	×		×
⊗	×	×	×	

	⊗	×	×	×
⊗	2	⊗	⊗	⊗
×	⊗		×	×
×	⊗	×		×
×	⊗	×	×	

...

	×	×	×	⊗
×		×	×	⊗
×	×		×	⊗
×	×	×		⊗
⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	5

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(a_2 a_3 a_4 a_5 b_1)(a_1 b_2 b_3 b_4 b_5) \\
 &(a_1 a_3 a_4 a_5 b_2)(a_2 b_1 b_3 b_4 b_5) \\
 &(a_1 a_2 a_4 a_5 b_3)(a_3 b_1 b_2 b_4 b_5) \\
 &(a_1 a_2 a_3 a_5 b_4)(a_4 b_1 b_2 b_3 b_5) \\
 &(a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4 b_5)(a_5 b_1 b_2 b_3 b_4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure B.4.: 2-covering of the standard example S_5

Figure B.5.: 1-covering of the Chevron C . The representation as would be given by Reuter has been omitted, as there are many overlaps.